

The mind: computation, emotion, physiology, physics, cosmology. Happiness, pleasure, morality, health. Consciousness, pleasure and pain in animals or AI. Is AI intelligence, or intuition? Is it safe to leave important decisions to AI?

Abstract

This article presents a comprehensive theory of consciousness that tries to answer the most fundamental questions of practical interest about the mechanisms of the human mind, self and consciousness, and also about the so-called 'Artificial Intelligence' technology in its current state: Will machines ever be able to surpass the human mind in every aspect? What is consciousness? Can a machine be conscious, in terms of self-awareness, pleasure or suffering? What animals can be considered to have consciousness, if any? And, of course, are we likely to live again after our death, and if so, in what form?

The main conclusions, drawn on the basis of purely scientific arguments, are the following:

A) Limits of artificial intelligence, with a high degree of likeliness:

A.1 As it is already widely assumed, with today's technology and in the foreseeable future, the practical use of these 'AI' tools has proved beyond doubt that they are not reliable and therefore must not be allowed to make important decisions without human supervision. In more technical terms, what has been developed so far is not real intelligence, but the machine equivalent of intuition or instinct.

A.2 Because of the limitations of their human creators, that is, us, these technologies will never be able to match or even approach, let alone surpass, human intelligence, even if they ever develop real intelligence instead of mere intuition or instinct. Technologies imitating phenomena like learning processes or sensations of live beings, management of abstract concepts, or natural selection of minds will be useless as long as they are designed by humans. The article includes a variety of arguments and proofs about these limitations, mostly independent but convergent, and based on, among other related subjects, the neural, physiological and computational modelling of concepts, Gödel's theorems, practical computer engineering and programming, and hypothetical artificial Darwinian selection, assisted or not, of machine computation models and simulation systems.

B) Hypothesis about consciousness, compatible with today's scientific knowledge and everyone's subjective sensations:

B.1 Consciousness, that is, awareness of one's existence, with the ability to feel sensations and emotions, including pleasure and pain, apparently requires the full integration, not only the mere coexistence, of two factors:

* The sentient part, which produces sensations, emotions, pleasure, suffering, will, subjective feeling of 'I'. This part is generally considered, when accepted at all, either of divine or transcendental nature (the 'soul'), or of purely physical nature, though not clearly identified so far, probably because today's theoretical physics does not include any phenomenon that could play this role in a way fully coherent with our own subjective experience, let alone with objective experiments. This article shows that this sentience may have a precise physical nature, unknown to today's theoretical physics, and inevitably impossible to measure by scientific procedures, but open to subjective analysis. In principle, this phenomenon can occur anywhere. Of course, its physical nature does not prevent us from believing that it has ultimately a divine origin, like all other physical phenomena.

* The cognitive or computational part, which is required to remember and be aware of the sentient part. It includes the concepts of reasoning, understanding, calculation, and memory. It can be considered purely algorithmic, pure information, and therefore in principle it can be developed by computing machines. The computing power of this part represents the main evolutionary advantage of consciousness. Although this part can be considered algorithmic in a broad sense, just as humans can be considered animals, in fact it is much more than that, it is a super algorithm, a generator of algorithms. However, it cannot produce subjective sensations by itself.

B.2 A consequence of the above is that, with today's electronic technology, it could perhaps be possible to build intelligent machines, but, for purely physical reasons, they would not be conscious, that is, they would not be aware of sensations or feelings, because the information circulating inside today's digital computers is not the integrated reflect of the physical phenomena representing it in these machines.

B.3 Another consequence is that consciousness is not an all-or-nothing phenomenon, but a quantitative one, depending on the power of the intelligent network and its degree of integration with the physical sentient part. Human-level consciousness can occur only when the cognitive part is fully integrated, bit by bit and in real time, with a compatible physical sentient part. A lesser degree of integration, or a less intense sentient part, or a less intelligent cognitive part, could result in a lower degree of consciousness. In consequence, we cannot be absolutely sure about when and to what degree a given physical dynamic system other than our human mind can develop consciousness.

C) The following consequence of hypothesis B) has been extensively confirmed by practice:

The physical properties of the sentient part imply by themselves strict limitations on the possible frequency and intensity of the sensations of pleasure that live creatures can experience. In humans, the possible strategies adequate to cope with these limitations have already been proclaimed by traditional wisdom, practically all major religions, and more or less directly even by modern medical science: moderation, self-control, empathy, reasonable diet and physical activity, etc. Failure to respect these rules implies not only the hypothetical typical punishments promised by religions, but also more immediate nefarious consequences in the form

of a variety of health problems that have been repeatedly verified to be less frequent in people respecting the abovementioned rules, either because of religious beliefs or for whatever other reason.

The second version of this article has been largely rewritten and analyses the compatibility of our theory with other famous or popular beliefs about the same subjects, including religions, scientific theories and their experimental findings, popular beliefs and traditional wisdom.

Keywords: Consciousness, self, algorithm, soul, strong and weak Artificial Intelligence, Gödel's theorems, pleasure and suffering, neuron, neural network, deep learning, evolution, punctuated equilibrium, religion, morality, common sense.

1. Introduction

The recent and often spectacular developments of the so-called Artificial Intelligence technology have brought a regain of popular interest in some questions previously limited to high-level science and philosophy, together with science-fiction literature:

- Will machines ever be able to surpass the human mind in every aspect?
- What is consciousness?
- Can a machine be conscious, in terms of self-awareness, pleasure or suffering?

Plus the traditional age-old questions:

- Is there a duality soul + body or only a body?
- What can we expect to happen after death?
- Which of hedonism or self-control is a better strategy?
- What is happiness? Is it merely the balance of pleasure over pain?
- Which animals or more generally creatures can be considered to have consciousness, if any?

So far, experience has shown that the latest developments of the so-called 'artificial intelligence' technology, materialized by the systems called 'Generative Pre-trained Transformers' (GPT), are far less reliable than the human mind as a source of information or a tool for decision-making, although they often provide spectacular results and may be useful for many purposes, including domains like arts and leisure, and also for practical decision-making but only if used by people with appropriate competences [70, 71]. However, this technology evolves continuously and it is not possible to predict now with certainty what it will be able to do in the future, but it may be possible to predict what it will **never** be able to do. For now, it seems that it still requires much non-technical human work [70].

This article tries to answer, on the basis of scientific arguments as rigorous as possible, and as independent as possible from the current degree of advancement of AI technology, the above fundamental questions. With this purpose, the article has been divided in the following main sections:

- The nature of intelligence and its limits, in biological and artificial systems.
- The nature of consciousness, that is, the 'awareness of self'.
- Comparison of our results with currently established beliefs and hypotheses about the same subjects.

2. Computational power and intelligence

In this section, we will try to determine in several different ways whether we humans can be expected to design and build machines as intelligent, or even more, than ourselves. Each of these different approaches has its own qualities and defaults, but they are complementary and, when considered together, they constitute a formidable argumentation in favour of the idea that human-made machines will never be able to approach the intellectual performance of the human mind.

There are several possible approaches to this problem, some of which will be further developed in the following sections:

- We can note that, if some mind A wants to understand the mechanism of another mind B, then in principle A must contain sufficient storage or room to include a full copy of B, plus the code or instructions necessary to represent and manage the fact that the copy of B is a simulation run inside A. In consequence, A must be strictly larger than B. This approach is not very rigorous and is not quantitative, but it is simple to understand and it describes the essence of the problem.
- As far as the author knows, the latest AI developments, the so-called 'deep learning' and 'generative models', are not an imitation of human reason, but of intuition. It is true that for some purposes, like face or voice recognition, human intuition can be very reliable, but for some other purposes the use of reason is necessary. There are many

human matters for which it would not be acceptable to be unable to reason or explain the arguments supporting one's statements. By contrast, today's AI tools seem unable to achieve a real understanding of most human concepts. This does not mean that these tools cannot be useful for many purposes, but always under human supervision. These points are further developed below.

- Gödel's incompleteness theorem provides a rigorous proof that the human mind cannot understand itself, but unfortunately this proof is not quantitative and is not particularly easy to understand. This proof is further explained and analysed below.

- A quantitative but not fully rigorous approach is provided by a comparative analysis of computer programs that 'understand' other programs, as do compilers and interpreters. This approach is also developed below and shows that, apparently, the factor by which the complexity of the 'understanding' mind must multiply that of the 'understood' mind seems to be at least a couple of orders of magnitude, and that it seems to depend to a significant degree on the characteristics of each particular case.

- A further limitation of AI systems results from them being essentially computer programs, and therefore subject to the general practical limits of these programs. This point is discussed in the section about debugging and testing.

2.1 *Intuition and reason*

In this section, we will try to explain the basic neural mechanisms of intuition, reason and learning, with the main purpose of evaluating to what degree today's technology can reproduce each of these phenomena.

2.1.1 *Parallel arrays*

In principle, the basic component of high-level neural functions is an assembly formed by a group of neurons with largely overlapping inputs and parallel outputs, which will be called '**parallel array**' in this document, or '**array**' for short. Each neuron of the array receives inputs from the outputs of a large number of other neurons, perhaps including some of their own array, and in turn sends its output through a single axon that may contact many other neurons of the same array or others. In principle, output → input connections within the same array can only be inhibitory, which means that their output signal tends to prevent target neurons from 'firing', that is, from emitting output signals. The purpose of this limitation is to prevent a deadlock of the array by positive feedback.

In principle, we can suppose that the output of a neuron can be either an all-or-nothing phenomenon, like a bit that can take the values 0 or 1, or a magnitude with more intermediate degrees, for example an integer from 0 to 255, or a real number between 0 and 1. In principle, all these options are compatible with the basic mechanism explained here. In addition, we will suppose that the neurons of the arrays are **plastic**, that is, the intensity of their response to some inputs can change, which is the mechanism of **learning**.

This simplified description is valid in principle for biological neurons as well as for artificial ones, whether made of pure software or including some hardware, and it is represented in Figure 1. It is essentially compatible with what we currently know about biological neurons as well as with the best-known models of artificial neurons.

2.1.2 *Representation of concepts and the role of reward*

The mechanism of a structured collection of neuronal arrays is essentially as follows, at least in the brains of superior animals: We suppose that the purpose of an individual array is to identify some pattern, for example a face, or a concept, such as truth, in an input formed by the outputs of the neurons of one or more other arrays (but NOT in the outputs of the neurons of the same array). The input can be, for example, visual information coded as pixels, or conceptual information coded as the presence or absence of diverse conceptual properties in some abstract line of thought. We also suppose that all the neurons of the array exert some degree of mutual inhibition on one another, so that in principle only one of them can fire at a given time. Let us suppose that, at some instant, with the current input information this is neuron N1. We also suppose that, in order to allow a neuron to fire without interruption in response to its current inputs, this neuron must receive continuously or at least periodically a signal of 'confirmation' or **reinforcement**, comparable to the '**reward**' of biological systems, which is identical for all the neurons of the array. The reinforcement, which is considered of **positive** sign when acting as a confirmation, increases the influence on the neurons of their inputs that are active at this moment, while it decreases that of the input that are not active. We assume that, if a positive reinforcement is not received regularly, the intensity of the influence of the neuronal inputs that are currently stimulating this neuron to fire diminishes progressively, and conversely its response to inputs that are not active at this moment increases gradually. As a result, after a certain time N1 may lose its capacity to inhibit

the other neurons of the array and it will be another neuron, N2, which will dominate the output of the array, representing another 'shape' or concept. Then, if N2 receives the reinforcement signal, it continues firing, otherwise another neuron N3 will take its place, and so on. This mechanism guarantees in principle that at a given time the output of the array represents only one of several incompatible concepts, and that this concept is, among those already known by the array (by innate initialization or previous learning), the one which best matches the collective input of the array at this moment. For example, for a pattern recognition array, the output may represent the concept of 'square', or 'triangle', but not both at the same time, and this will require the existence in the array of at least one neuron that fires when the input has the form of a square, and at least another which fires when it has a triangular shape.

The representation of concepts by neurons has a considerable experimental support [1, 2, 3].

Figure 1: Neuronal arrays

This figure represents a structured and connected system of parallel neuronal arrays, as described in the text, visible at the left of the figure. The right part represents an amplified section of one array, showing a few neurons and their connections. For clarity, the represented numbers of whole arrays and their connections, and of neurons and their connections inside one array, are far lower than in real systems, whether biological or artificial. The divisions or frontiers between arrays are not necessarily physical, they may be only logical, and even blurry. Of the possible control connections, only one line for reinforcement and another for absolute sensitivity have been represented, but they may be multiple, and there may be control connections of other types. The neurons are represented with arbitrary polygonal shapes, with no functional or geometric meaning, to avoid possible confusions with the shape of biological neurons or the symbols commonly used to represent logical gates or circuits.

2.1.3 Learning

It follows from the above description that the array must contain at least one neuron per identifiable concept. Therefore, in order to learn new concepts, there are in principle two possibilities:

- If at some point a certain concept is represented by **several neurons of the array**, learning a new variant of the concept will require **dividing this group of neurons** into at least two parts, one for the old concept and another for the variant. For example, if it is necessary to distinguish a new shape 'square with round corners', some of the neurons of the original 'square' group will change the strength of their input connections to represent only squares with sharp corners, while the other neurons of the group will henceforth represent only square shapes with round corners. Obviously, this way of learning can be applied only a limited number of times, unless there is a mechanism in the array by which the most active neurons duplicate themselves (neuronal reproduction) before becoming alone in the representation of their associated concept. In biological systems, since cell reproduction is not instantaneous, it must take place with sufficient anticipation.

- If neuronal reproduction does not take place inside the neuronal array, then sooner or later the representation of new concepts will have to be 'transferred' to another array where neurons are still redundant for the representation of concepts, either because it has not needed to learn very much in the past or because this redundancy is guaranteed by regular neuronal reproduction (**neurogenesis**) inside the array. It would seem that this is what happens in the brain of mammals, including adult humans, in which the storage of new memories is 'delegated' mainly to the hippocampus. There is presently an ongoing controversy about the occurrence of neurogenesis in the adult human brain [4], but it seems clear that its complete absence would be incompatible with the formation of new memories in human adults in the context of the neuronal model presented here. In children and perhaps adolescents, a model of learning based only on original neuronal redundancy seems more likely than in adults.

In neuronal arrays built according to the above model and learning without significant neurogenesis, sooner or later new memories would partially and irreversibly erase those of the previous learning cycles, which is what may occur in very old people and also in simple designs of artificial neural networks. In fact, the author does not know of any real solution to this problem in today's 'deep learning' technologies. Extensive learning without neuronal reproduction would require a model completely different from the one presented here, which is essentially equivalent to the artificial neural networks of today's AI technology and also seems to agree with what we know about biological neurons. We can also remark that practical experience seems to indicate that, in the human brain, in normal conditions new memories never disappear, although depending on their use they may become increasingly difficult to retrieve.

2.1.4 Neural inputs

The inputs of the neurons of the arrays are essentially of the following types:

- **Information / data**, representing the internal and external context or environment. The sensitivity of plastic neurons to these signals can evolve with learning.

- **Control signals**, for example absolute excitability, or reinforcement. In principle, even plastic neurons cannot change their sensitivity to these signals.

At least in superior animals, reinforcement is quantitative and can have a sign: **positive reinforcement** is reward, understood as confirmation or pleasure, and **negative reinforcement**, which amounts to dissuasion, displeasure, or 'punishment', induces neurons to diminish their response to their current set of inputs. We will not try here to elucidate whether in biological systems this requires one or more physical connections, nor whether the gradual decrease of the sensitivity of plastic neurons to their current inputs is spontaneous or results also / only from the negative reinforcement resulting from the effort developed by the organism, which in any case plays an essential role.

We can note that, in biological systems, although the reinforcement mechanism in arrays can be considered essentially equivalent in the logical aspect to the preceding description, in terms of real physical connections the structure seems to be somewhat different. In short, the positive reinforcement input is merely an excitatory input devoid of plasticity, that is, always effective, or just stronger than the other, plastic inputs. Neurons tend to anticipate incoming signals in order to prevent excessive tensions or even damage: when a neuron receives a strong / unconditional stimulus forcing it to fire, it increases its sensitivity to the already active but less intense inputs that could warn the neuron in the future that a stronger stimulus is about to arrive. This is the mechanism found experimentally for conditioned responses in terms of elementary neuronal reactions, even in very simple animals and without array grouping [5]. In principle, we will assume a complementary inverse mechanism for the negative reinforcement resulting from pain or displeasure. We can also remark that the neural events at this level of detail consist mainly of trains of spikes, unlike the more

continuous logical events at the logical higher lever described before, and that the timing of the spikes at this low level is likely far more critical than at the logical higher level.

In principle, we can assume that in biological brains, at least in humans and superior vertebrates, the reward signals use the neurotransmitter dopamine, with some participation, apparently less direct, of serotonin. In this respect, further explanations and discussions are given in section 5.3.1.

2.1.5 *Strategies and intermediate rewards*

In superior animals, a typical course of action or thought consists in many steps, in each of which the combinations of inputs of the neurons of at least one array change according to the abovementioned laws. The most elementary steps are usually grouped into higher-level steps that can be considered concepts and will be called here **strategies**. In turn, these strategies can be part of higher-level strategies, and so on. For example, there may be a strategy consisting in going from A to E, which in turn is an ordered set formed by the strategies consisting in going from A to B, from B to C, from C to D, and from D to E. In turn, each of these may consist of several steps, such as A → a, a → b, and b → B, and so on. We can also note that there may be several different strategies suitable to go from A to E, and that each strategy of a certain level can be part of more than one strategy of a higher level. In addition the strategies may be 'parametrized' with variable arguments, for example the general strategy 'go to' may have two parameters or arguments, the origin and the destination, plus perhaps reference intermediate points. The strategies may correspond to simple or complex actions of the real world, or to the manipulation of abstract concepts, especially in humans or superior animals. We can also suppose, as our intuitive insight indicates, that composite strategies can comprise much more than mere successions of steps, including at least the fundamental features of computer programs such as 'if-else' branching, loops, stacks, variables, pointers and references, subroutines and functions, etc., all this being most probably innate. The mind of superior animals also probably includes circuits for intuitive elementary statistical calculations: for example, everybody is capable of realizing intuitively how probable an event is on the basis of the frequency observed for its occurrences.

According to the preceding considerations, the correct performance of the neurons requires that their set of inputs include at least the following information:

- The state of the current environment, external and internal, felt through the sensory organs and their associated analysers, or imagined inside the brain for simulation and design purposes.
- Information about the current strategy and perhaps also some of its associated higher-level ones.

At least in superior animals, in order to allow the progressive learning of complex strategies, each relevant step will have an associated confirmation signal or **reward**, which validates the fulfilment of this step and, for all steps except the last, is considered an **intermediate reward**. Rewards are calculated in specialized arrays with large output ranges, whose input, like those of the other arrays, represents the context and the current strategy. We can distinguish **final** or **unconditional rewards**, which correspond to low-level physiological functions, are innate and are not subject to plasticity, from intermediate rewards, whose activation is learned in the reward centres much in the same way as the actions of arrays of other types, on the basis of rewards of higher strength and less or no plasticity.

In certain adverse conditions, the predominance of final rewards over the more intelligent but weaker learned intermediate rewards can bypass all the corresponding strategy steps associated to these rewards and therefore result in enormous problems like those caused by substances stimulating directly the so-called 'pleasure centres' of the brain. In these cases, it is impossible to extinguish the addictive strategies by pure force of will, because conscious will is a part of what is bypassed by the addiction. However, it is often possible to extinguish the addictive strategy indirectly, or at least diminish its craving, by performing it with no final reward or with a final reward much weaker than the original in relation to the fatigue or discomfort that the strategy causes. Unlike the force of will, this fatigue or discomfort is effective to extinguish the addictive strategy. This method takes advantage of the limited analytical capacities of the arrays of the middle and lowest brain levels, where rewards are calculated: they are strong but not very clever. The option of progressively reducing the active principle psychoactive instead of suppressing it completely at once has the advantage of avoiding a brutal abstinence syndrome. We will further analyse this phenomenon in the sections about consciousness. However, we will not try to elucidate less important details, for example to determine whether superior biological brains have only one centralized reinforcement centre or several ones, either in logical or

physical terms, and in the second case which are their respective functions, which is of limited relevance for our purposes.

The use of intermediate rewards to learn each step of a complex course of action implies a further requirement: since the rewards of the intermediate steps must be ultimately confirmed by the achievement of the final unconditional reward, which may occur much later, a successful learning procedure requires, at its termination, 'unwinding' the succession of steps that has been effectively performed, so that each one can be reinforced by the already active final reinforcement, which in general will last for some time. Obviously, this procedure will be possible only if the relevant information associated to these steps has been previously stored somewhere in the individual's memory. In principle, the 'unwinding' procedure can take place during either sleep or wakefulness, as long as the organism is reasonably relaxed and has nothing better to do, for example when during a peaceful meal one remembers the different actions that have preceded this meal. It seems likely that this procedure occurs in the hippocampus, or an analogous structure, in the animals that have one.

2.1.6 Structures of concepts, innate concepts and formation of new concepts

It is important to understand that the sophisticated mechanism described in the preceding sections, with its complexity and its weaknesses, is not necessary to develop intelligence, but to learn. In principle, the intelligence of a structure with invariable connection strengths, such as a computer program, is limited only by the intellectual power of its creators, as we will see later. However, a system that does not include reinforcement or a similar mechanism will be unable to learn anything, no matter its intelligence.

A much more formidable problem is the formation of new concepts, which, in contrast to the acquisition of new values for a given concept, should require in principle a complicated collective rearrangement of the neuronal arrays, most likely with the use of specialized 'placeholder' multipurpose pre-existing arrays. The author does not know of the inclusion of any such mechanism in today's AI systems.

Another formidable problem, which is perhaps the one that makes the insurmountable difference between the human mind and human-made machines, is the predefinition of the **thousands of concepts necessary for logical reasoning** and for **common sense**, plus their **relations**. It is well known that the human brain has a built-in intuition of nearly all the concepts necessary for the practical application of logic and mathematics, which is the reason why in the 20th century some prominent mathematicians, like Hilbert and Russell, felt the need to treat logic and mathematics in a purely formal way, in principle to avoid the lack of reliability of human intuition in these domains. This ultimately resulted in a total failure, not only because Gödel's theorems preclude it, but also because the use of strictly formal logic and mathematics is extremely cumbersome in comparison to its innate intuitive counterpart, which makes this formalism inapplicable for practical purposes: for example, who uses the formal definition $\{\emptyset, \{\emptyset\}, \{\emptyset, \{\emptyset\}\}, \{\emptyset, \{\emptyset\}, \{\emptyset, \{\emptyset\}\}\}, \{\emptyset, \{\emptyset, \{\emptyset, \{\emptyset\}\}\}, \{\emptyset, \{\emptyset, \{\emptyset, \{\emptyset, \{\emptyset\}\}\}\}\}$ of the number 5 to count 5 objects? Furthermore, the mental management of common human activities requires the use, intuitive in humans, of thousands of predefined or learned concepts related at least to human anatomy, physiology and internal sensations, human relations, emotions and traditions, biological, geological and urban environment, meteorology, food, economy, tools, machines, transport, clothing, and many other domains, with innumerable relations of diverse types between these concepts. Genuine understanding by a machine of a large part of these concepts would require this machine to develop and experience real human practical activities, which seems highly utopic with the technology of the foreseeable future. Today's AI technology manages all these concepts and their relations by merely applying statistical methods to their mentions or references in libraries of electronic texts, images, sounds, or multimedia storage in general, without really understanding them, let alone feeling them, in any way.

In sum, our knowledge and experience of human mental processes and our practice with machines as intelligent as we have been able to achieve seem to indicate that **both intuition and reason** are, or can be, materialized by **arrays of parallel neurons**, capable of learning, and that **both deal with concepts**, whose treatment may be in principle either genetically predefined or learned by experience. However, it would seem that **reason** requires in addition the ability to manage a great number of **abstract concepts arranged in a complex multilevel structure and their mutual relations**, with the capacity of performing logic, that is, **complex linear successions of processes of concept detection and chaining compatible with abstract or formal logic**, with the additional possibility of remembering all the relevant conceptual processes that have been previously invoked. In other words, the potential achievements of a single array of parallel neurons, no matter how big and multi-layered it might be, as in today's AI, are limited to the generation of

simple intuitions, without the possibility of reproducing any chain of steps that could have led to the final result. By contrast, **reason** would require a **structured arrangement of many such arrays**, far **more complicated than any such array** by itself. In fact, it seems, as we deduce in the following sections, that the complexity of these arrangements far exceeds the collective intellectual capacity of these arrangements themselves, with the important consequences that we are unable to build machines like ourselves and that we cannot even know whether our reasoning abilities must necessarily be innate or can be learned, and in this case how this can be done.

2.1.7 Treatment of concepts in recent and older AI designs

It may be interesting to note that, in principle, a neuronal parallel array as defined above is roughly equivalent to one **layer** of today's artificial neural networks, so one could naively think that, by using neural networks with a great number of layers and applying techniques of 'deep learning' to them, the appropriate high-order concepts would automatically take place in these layers, with one concept per layer or part of it. The problem is that this approach is far too simplistic, because it seems to confuse **size** with **complexity**, and also complexity with **analytical power** and **usefulness**, in contradiction with even the most elementary theories of complexity and chaos [6, 7, 8]. More precisely, nothing guarantees that this procedure would implement the concepts in their appropriate relative layer level, let alone their relations. So far, this is what the practical use of today's AI has shown: the producers of these technologies have merely put this procedure into practice and see what happened, just in case the results could be useful in some practical way, if only for recreational purposes for lack of anything more useful.

In terms of analytical power in speech generation, systems based fundamentally on deep learning could be compared for example to parrots: both learn by imitation and even have a limited intuition of the meaning of what they say, but without really understanding it, although it is clear that AI machines have a considerably larger vocabulary than animals. By contrast, an artificial speech generation system driven by precise logic in order to express an objective fact, for example 'it is eight o'clock in the morning', can be considered to understand properly what it is saying, though not necessarily also its consequences for the user of the system.

In more academic and traditional terms, the design of systems based on neural networks of great regularity, with massive automated learning, partly assisted or not, but with little logic, with the hope that sooner or later they will acquire reason and common sense spontaneously, can be considered an application of the 'tabula rasa' principle, which postulates essentially that the mind of newborns has no significant built-in content and acquires progressively its abilities only by learning. Many authors have claimed, and scientific evidence has shown, that in fact there is a significant amount of innate abilities and instinctive behaviour predefined in the human brain at birth [9], although obviously a considerable part of the future brain content must be learned. Experience also seems to show that pure regular multi-layered neural networks work only for limited purposes and that at least some predefined procedures and more refined architectures must be included by design in AI systems no matter how deeply they learn later [10], even only to make them produce something far from perfect but useful in practice. For example, it can be useful to translate texts without really understanding them but with enough accuracy to significantly reduce the manual work necessary to achieve a correct translation. However, these procedures and refinements cannot be learned massively and must be included manually.

Additionally, we can note that some designs of AI systems of previous generations, mainly the well-known '**expert systems**', although useful for many purposes when used appropriately, had an inverse design ultimately affected by the same problem: they consisted mainly of a structure of high-level concepts and their relations, but the individual implementation of each of these concepts and relations was too simple, and even the concept superstructure was likely too simple also. As in the present, the reason was that this structure had to be defined 'by hand', without the possibility of learning it through massive processes that could be performed automatically with little or no human supervision, because this could only produce a structure too simple no matter its size and number of levels.

In sum, the remaining fundamental problem is still whether the manual task of completely defining the necessary concepts and their relations will always be ultimately overwhelmed by the sheer size and complexity of the natural mental structures that must be imitated. The following sections provide several approaches to this specific problem.

2.2 Gödel's incompleteness theorems

Gödel's (first) incompleteness theorem is a rigorous proof that all formal effective logical theories contain undecidable statements, that is, there are statements formulated in the language of the considered theory that can neither be proved nor disproved by this theory.

Therefore, to deduce from this theorem that the human mind cannot understand its own mechanism, and therefore cannot build artificial copies of itself, the following considerations apply:

- It should be possible to assimilate the human mind to an effective formal logical theory. The complete detailed proof of this statement could require a whole book, so will sketch here only a concise proof of this statement in two steps:

First, the computational aspect of the human mind, which is its only aspect relevant to understand things, can be reproduced by a computer built according to today's technology. It seems clear that the mechanism of any individual neuron can be simulated by a computer program, as accurate and realistic as necessary, though most probably horribly complicated. Then, a higher-level program can calculate successively the reaction of each neuron to its inputs at a given time and its influence on other neurons, in time steps as small as necessary, and repeat this cycle any number of times. The fact that such monstrous program would have a disastrous performance and that its complexity would far exceed the practical abilities of any human team does not prevent it from being theoretically appropriate, which is the only necessary condition for the purpose of our proof.

Second, once we have established the theoretical existence of this program, we must prove that it is equivalent to a formal logical theory. In principle, this should be possible by defining (many) axioms of the form: when the register N1 contains the value N2 and the instruction pointer contains N3 and the memory cell at N4 contains value N5, and (...), and we are at instant NT, then at the next computing cycle $NT + 1$ the register N6 will change its content to N7, the memory cell at N8 will change its content to N9, etc. The symbols N? may refer to individual numbers like 5 or formulas involving other numeric parameters like the contents of registers or memory cells referred to by numbers. The elementary time step can be chosen as small as necessary. Like the computer program, this formal logic theory would be monstrous and impossible to put into practice, but it would make conceptually possible for us to apply Gödel's incompleteness theorem to the human mind or to any team of human minds.

- It could be argued that Gödel's theorem implies only that a certain statement, artificially built and therefore most probably devoid of practical significance, cannot be proved or disproved by the human mind. More precisely, this statement can be classified within the broader category of self-referring statements, of which the best-known examples, such as the declaration that 'what I am saying is a lie' really do not have practical significance. However, in the case of Gödel's statement, it is precisely its self-reference what confers it its practical importance: when a human mind is trying to understand its own mechanism in order to reproduce it in a machine, logically it should be using precisely the part of the mind whose purpose is to understand the mechanism of parts of the mind like itself, which not only must inescapably be included in the future artificial mind, but are probably the most important part of it. In consequence, in the design and construction of machines as intelligent as possible, Gödel's statement self-reference, far from reflecting an anecdotal or amusing circumstance with no practical implications, represents an unsurmountable barrier preventing any intelligent being from designing or building complete artificial copies of itself, let alone improved versions.

- The fact that Gödel's theorem proves only the existence of one undecidable / unprovable statement could be misinterpreted in the sense that the theory under consideration could prove all the other possible statements that can be built within this theory. However, this is not exact, if only because if we add the truth of the undecidable statement to the theory as an axiom, in principle we obtain a theory equivalent to the first one except for the new axiom, at least as long as this axiom does not interfere with the original ones, which can be almost taken for granted for many iterations of this procedure if the theory is as large and complicated as the human mind. Then the new theory will have its own different undecidable statement, and so on. Therefore, in fact a given theory can give rise to a substantial number of statements that it can neither prove nor disprove. What Gödel's theorem does not provide is an estimation of the total number of undecidable statements that can arise from a given theory.

- Our application of Gödel's theorem could perhaps be misunderstood in the sense that it does not reflect a lack of capacity, but a structural obstacle that can be overcome, in the same way that you cannot scratch your right hand with your right hand, but you can use your right hand to scratch your left hand, which is equally complicated. However, this

does not apply to our proof, because if you can understand some system, you can also understand any equivalent copy of it. The limits of systems like the two hands of the example apply only to material objects, not to information.

- Formally, Gödel's theorem cannot exclude a situation like the following: Some system A understands another substantially different system B, and inversely B can also understand A, although none of them can understand itself. Intuitively, we feel that this is unlikely, because we feel that A can understand B because the intelligence and complexity of A are greater, though perhaps comparable, to those of B, and vice-versa. Therefore, in principle a certain mind could understand others with a similar complexity, but not more complex, and even this conclusion would not be rigorous. However, perhaps it might be possible to establish rigorously at least some partial order reflecting complexity between systems subject to relations of the type 'A understands B', on the basis of the fact that this kind of relation necessarily reflects the existence of some common vocabulary shared by A and B, or a subset of the vocabulary of A equivalent or isomorphic to a subset of that of B. This would be far too complicated to attempt it here, but some approximate indications in this respect can be found in the section about quantitative estimations of the complexity and power of simpler programs.

In sum, Gödel's theorem proves, in a logically rigorous way, that there is a limit to the intelligence of any machine that can be designed or built by humans, and that this limit results from the limits of the human mind itself when acting as designer or builder. In this respect, we can remark that in principle nothing precludes the possible existence of machines made of transistors, quantum gates, nanobots or whatever, and more intelligent than humans for any activity, but only as long as these machines are designed and built by superhuman minds. However, this theorem does not quantify the degree of superhumanness that would be required for that task. We will try to estimate this degree in the next sections.

2.3 Quantitative estimations of superhumanness

In this section, we will try to estimate the minimal difference of size or complexity that can be expected between some mind A and another mind B, supposing that A is capable of understanding the mechanism of B and that in both minds the ratios complexity / size and analytical power / complexity are approximately optimal.

Since we have proved that it is impossible for humans to perform this estimation for human minds, we will use instead, at least in a first attempt, much simpler models involving computer programs related by a relation that we can consider comparable to understanding:

- The 'understood' program is a small program written in a well-known and powerful computer language, with essentially all the features of this language in a compact unit, not divisible into loosely coupled parts that could represent added size but not complexity. The 'understanding' program is a compiler or interpreter of this language. For our comparison, it is important to understand not only the difference between size and complexity, but also the level at which complexity is relevant. A compiler can compile programs much larger than itself, as long as they are written in its language, and also more complex than itself, but only as long as this complexity does not affect the process of compiling. For example, an enormous program implementing a horrendously complex neural network can be compiled without problem as long as the compiler is allocated enough storage and process time, whereas the complexity of the neural network will affect only the processes of designing this network and analyzing its output. Therefore, for our comparisons, we have used as 'understood' simple programs performing non-trivial mathematical calculations such as finding the prime factors of a number, and for the 'understanding' compiler or interpreter, we have selected simple but complete open-source compilers or interpreters of well-known computer languages, such as Small C, Tiny C, Small Basic, etc. The reasons for choosing simple implementations were to have a design as open as possible and also to avoid counting as analytical power the size of features included by commercial programs to increase usability or performance.

- The 'understood' program is the computer implementation of the axioms of a 'toy' formal theory such as those proposed in [11] to explain formal theories, and the 'understanding' program is a program that tries to determine whether some input written in the language of the theory is a theorem of the theory, that is, can be deduced directly or indirectly from the axioms of the theory, or not.

We have used preferentially for the comparisons, when possible, the source code of the programs, without the input / output sections. Complementary comparisons have been performed on the object code, in principle excluding statically linked libraries.

The results, which will not be fully detailed here, have a significant variability, depending on the selected functions and tools, but we have found consistently the following:

- With the option involving compilers, a direct comparison of the programs indicates that the quantities corresponding to the 'understanding' program are larger than those of the 'understood' program by factors ranging approximately from **50 to 100**. However, if we count the rules or grammar of the computer language as part of the 'understood' system (they are already part of the 'understanding' system, by definition), the results are significantly lower, in the range 2 - 10.

- With the option involving 'toy' formal theories, the ratios are lower, in the range of 2 to 4 if the axioms are expressed as a computer program, and somewhat higher if they are expressed in the 'language' of the theory.

Of course, the results of these comparisons are applicable in principle only to small systems, and we have no rigorous proof that the differences will be of the same order at the level of complexity of the human mind. However, the differences between the comparisons involving compilers and those involving 'toy' theories could be interpreted in principle as faint indications that the differences between the 'understanding' and the 'understood' programs may increase with the size / complexity of these programs, perhaps because the amount of connections and the number of possible cases is not a linear but a combinatorial / exponential function of the size.

We can obtain a further reasonably realistic reference if we count as part of the 'understanding' system the program code necessary to design the compiler. The machine necessary for this task is the human mind itself, which we do not fully understand, but we can estimate its size. With the approximate reference of around 10^{15} synapses in the human brain, a conservative estimation, at one byte per synapse, could be established at around 10^{12} synapses, and therefore 10^{12} bytes, for the whole human brain. Of course, not all these synapses may be necessary to design compilers, but we can note that no other animal, even with a comparable or only slightly lower number of synapses, is even remotely capable of designing compilers. In consequence, in principle we can assume that at least a significant part of the total amount of synapses of the human brain are necessary to design compilers. According to these considerations, we will adopt here a reference size around 10 GB (10^{10} bytes) as a conservative estimation of the size of the part of the human mind necessary to design and build compilers. In consequence, even if we count the full compiler as part of the 'understood' program, the size of this program will not exceed a limit around 100 KB (10^5 bytes), which is an upper limit for the size of the compilers reviewed in this section. The final result of this conservative evaluation is that the size / complexity of the 'understanding' program must be greater than that of the 'understood' program by a factor around **10^5** , that is, five orders of magnitude.

All these results seem to indicate that the incompleteness proved by Gödel's theorem, far from being an anecdotal exception affecting only a few situations irrelevant in practice, reflects in fact a significant difference of orders of magnitude, of 2 orders at least, between the 'understanding' and 'understood' systems.

Finally, we can also note that the results of this section exclude in principle situations where a system A understands another system B and vice-versa, no matter how different these systems are, as described in the section about Gödel's theorem, because this would imply that A is at least about 50 or 100 times more complex than B while B is also at least about 50 or 100 times more complex than A, which is obviously impossible.

2.4 Reliability of computer programs. Debugging and testing.

AI systems are essentially a particular class of computer programs, and therefore their production is subject to the general limits of the software industry. In particular, as all computer technicians know, it is humanly impossible to produce at the first attempt a program usable in practice and completely free from errors. More precisely, the data of the author show that it is practically impossible, even for intelligent and experienced programmers, to write at the first attempt a program with a few hundred lines of code completely free from errors. It is also very difficult to spot errors in the programs of others just by looking at them, although for that purpose the limit may be a little higher and more variable, around a thousand lines. Therefore, in order to produce programs of reasonable reliability, the software industry must make extensive use of the procedures of debugging and testing programs, which consist in verifying manually that, in all cases that can be tested in practice, the results of the program coincide with those expected in this situation. If errors are detected, the program is corrected and tested again, and the cycle is repeated until no error is found at all in the testing time available according to economic considerations.

This procedure has the following characteristics:

- It affects ALL computer programs, including those for which the expected results can be established with absolute certainty, as in financial software.
- The use of automated testing tools, although inevitable in some situations, is not a solution, because these tools are also programs and therefore are subject in turn to the same limitations.
- It is absolutely impossible to produce any software product suitable for professional or domestic use and absolutely free from errors, no matter the resources invested in the testing procedure. The software that we use in practice is reasonable reliable for the use that we make of it because in general the presence of errors is limited to the less frequent situations. However, ALL programs of commercial size have errors: otherwise, hackers would not even exist, because they would have no vulnerabilities to exploit, and software producers would not need to publish corrective updates.

Although this problem is already serious enough for classical software, in the case of AI it is far worse, for obvious reasons: since the expected results of the tests must be calculated manually, how on earth could we test a software supposedly endowed with superhuman intelligence, whose result by definition cannot be calculated by humans? Even software intended to merely match the performance of the human mind cannot be properly tested in domains that do not admit rigorous mathematical procedures, like psychology, sociology, or even disciplines with only a scientific part, such as medicine or economics. Furthermore, it is impossible to test programs dealing with the evolution of human groups or societies over years, because, by the time the program has been tested and declared reasonably free from errors, its conditions of application might have substantially changed, spoiling the validity of the testing procedure.

This limitation is probably the most firmly established and verified of all those discussed in this article for AI technology, so it is difficult to understand why prominent software experts who have been competent programmers are expressing the opinion that machines designed and built by humans will be able to match or surpass the overall performance of the human mind in the future. Perhaps the potential capacities of automated learning technologies, which are relatively new and somewhat different from classical software, are being overestimated. It is also possible that the power of their 'evolutionary' aspect has been overestimated, as discussed in the next section.

2.5 Hypothetical Darwinian evolution of programs

It is currently accepted, in general, that human intelligence appeared on Earth thanks to an evolutionary process starting from elementary chemical substances and supposedly driven by the natural selection of the organisms best adapted to their environment. In principle, this theory could have suggested to some optimists the idea that superhuman intelligence could be made to emerge from some artificial procedure of 'natural selection' of programs, and even that in some way machine learning procedures could bear some resemblance to natural selection in their hypothetical capability of generating superhuman intelligence.

However, even a preliminary analysis shows that evolutionary selection is impossible in practice at this scale, because an environment so complicated as that of the human species is strictly impossible to simulate in any computer with even the least degree of practical validity. Even far less limited aspects of this problem, such as economic simulations, have been a complete failure, featuring pitifully simplistic caricatures of human behavior like the notorious and largely criticized 'homo economicus' [12], so that in practice the predictions of economic models are essentially as reliable as random predictions, and it is the intelligence, common sense and experience of economists which makes the difference between serious economics and divination.

Furthermore, nowadays the theory of evolution by natural selection alone is pure ideology. In the scientific aspect, this theory is obsolete at least since the discovery of DNA and its related processes in the 1950s. It is possible to prove in several ways that no evolution of species driven only by the natural selection of the organisms best adapted to their environment can have resulted in the emergence of human intelligence on Earth. Some arguments supporting this claim are provided in the following sections.

2.5.1 Probability of appearance of the first cells

The procedure of natural selection of organisms is subject to a fundamental restriction: it can affect only organisms capable of reproduction. In consequence, it cannot have taken place before the appearance of the first cell or similar

organism. Darwinian theories often underestimate, ignore or hide the phase of evolution when cells capable of self-reproduction still did not exist, but this is not acceptable for the following reasons:

- It has been suggested that some molecules such as RNA show some duplication capabilities [13], but these capabilities are very limited and occur only in very particular laboratory environments, and so far no experiment has shown anything remotely comparable to a spontaneous evolution from elementary prebiotic molecules to RNA capable of suitable duplication and catalytic activity. In addition, the appearance by chance of the first RNA molecules capable of reproduction is subject to the probabilistic problem explained below for cells.

- The appearance by mere chance of self-reproducing organisms like the most elementary cells would have required a time exponentially greater than the age of the universe estimated by the Big Bang theory. There are many possible ways to estimate this time, for example on the basis of the probability of appearance by chance of the correct sequence of nucleotides, or of the correct arrangement of molecules inside the volume of a cell. In this text, we will provide a considerably underestimated value for the number of possible sequences of the DNA of the first cells. With the reference of several million base pairs (bp) for the genome of modern bacteria (smaller organisms, like viruses and other parasite organisms, would not provide a valid reference because they cannot survive on their own, and at these times there were no other organisms to parasitize), we can estimate, with some margin, for the genome of the first bacteria a size around 1 million bp. We add a further margin by supposing that, unlike in today's prokaryotes, this DNA is relatively inefficient, only around a third of its content being really useful. This amounts to ~110000 codons, which allows $\sim 20^{110000} \sim 10^{140000}$ possible sequences of amino acids. Even if we assume that these combinations could have been tried in, say, 1 femtosecond each, at every possible location of the universe simultaneously, which of course is a wild overestimation, and that an enormous number of these combinations could have resulted in viable bacteria, this number would hardly be much greater than the present number of bacterial species, which in turn is not even remotely comparable to the total number of atoms in the universe. In consequence, at most these corrections reduce our estimation by about 10^{200} , resulting in about 10^{139800} sequences. We will add a further margin by supposing that the order of the genes in the genome is essentially irrelevant, which is far from obvious in real biological systems. To apply this correction, we must divide by the number of possible permutations of N objects, that is, N!, where N is the number of genes in the genome. Even if N were of the order of 2000 - 3000, as in modern bacteria, N! would still not exceed 10^{10000} . Therefore, in total all these correction factors would result in approximately 10^{129800} combinations, which is practically the same as the initial estimation for all practical purposes (FAPP). We will neglect possible corrections in the other sense, for example to take into account the real number of locations of the universe compatible with the development of life.

In consequence, in principle we can assume that even the most moderate evaluations of the time necessary for the spontaneous random appearance of live cells in our universe are of the order of at least around 10^{100000} times the currently estimated age of the universe. Of course, even a correct DNA sequence would be useless without the correct machinery necessary to replicate it and synthesize proteins. To take this machinery into account, we could make an estimation based on the number of possible arrangements of molecules inside the volume of a cell, which would give a vastly greater result than the one based on DNA only.

In sum, even a considerable underestimation of the probability of spontaneous appearance of live cells in our universe shows that either **the real age of the universe is, for all practical purposes, infinitely greater than its currently estimated age**, or **the first structures of life did not appear by chance**, but because the physical laws of our universe contain some '**predisposition**' to generate spontaneously these structures. This does not mean necessarily that this predisposition has been prepared by intelligent beings, that is, it may be only '**intensional**' rather than 'intentional', as explained in detail in [14], but what we know about the evolution of life on Earth cannot be explained without admitting the existence, at the origin of the universe of the Big Bang, of some predefined plan for the future appearance of at least the first organisms capable of reproduction.

In principle, this restriction does not invalidate directly a hypothetical procedure of artificial evolution of intelligent programs, but it provides a first argument in favor of the opinion that the power of the mechanism of natural selection that has occurred on Earth has been largely overestimated.

2.5.2 *Beneficial and deleterious mutations*

It is clear that truly random mutations occurring inside an organized system can produce beneficial effects only in a very small proportion of the total number of events. For example, changing at random a character in a computer program will most likely result in a compile error or a wrong calculation, and practically never in an improvement of the program. Therefore, unless the changes occurring between consecutive generations of organisms are driven, at least partially, by a pre-planned mechanism as the one already explained for the phase preceding the appearance of the first cells, these changes cannot be beneficial on average. However, the small proportion of beneficial random changes can persist in populations of unicellular organisms, because, even if this proportion is insignificant, these changes can be conserved and exponentially propagated by cell reproduction. By contrast, in multicellular organisms, the reproduction of cells affected by beneficial mutations cannot compensate the loss or malfunction of much higher amounts of cells affected by deleterious mutations in many other locations of the organism, and anybody who knows what cancer is can understand what can be the consequences of massive exponential cell reproduction inside a multicellular organism.

2.5.3 *Visibility of evolutionary changes*

In order to be favored by evolution, the changes caused by mutations in cells must be '**visible**' to natural selection, that is, they must create or improve functions that imply a significant interaction with the environment of the organism. However, as has been already profusely remarked, if evolution occurs only by small steps, as the original theory of natural selection postulated in order to limit the harmful effects of the predominant deleterious mutations, the appearance of functional organs visible to natural selection is not possible, because the first small steps cannot be reasonably supposed to produce even a partially functional organ visible to natural selection. On the contrary, at these early steps, the result would be most likely a dead weight, harmful for the organism in most circumstances. On this basis, it was proposed that the evolution of live beings has not been a continuous succession of small changes, but that periodically more dramatic changes must have occurred as well. This is the theory of 'punctuated equilibrium' [15, 16], which, as one could easily expect, was not well received by evolutionists. However, it was later profusely shown that, in the evolution of life, the appearance of new organs has most often resulted from the sudden duplication and subsequent gradual change of function of a pre-existing organ [17, 18]. In principle, the survival of the organisms subject to this kind of sudden and traumatic mutation can be explained only by a pre-planned and 'intentionally' or 'intentionally' massive occurrence of this kind of changes.

By contrast, sexual reproduction allows gradual changes without mutations, by combining the characteristics of the two parents, which in general will result in a phenotype not necessarily worse than those of the parents, but just different, and therefore most often viable. However, such changes can occur only within the genotype of a given species, so new species can appear only as the result of important mutations with much higher probabilities of disastrous results than sexual reproduction, unless resulting from a pre-existing plan.

2.5.4 *Anticipation of fitness for purpose*

One of the most striking aspects of the evolution of life on Earth is that, at many points, there had been important changes, often traumatic and potentially fatal, that have favored organisms living millions of years later, whereas natural selection is supposed to favor the organisms best adapted to their current environment. Also strikingly, no proponent of the theory of evolution by pure natural selection seems to have noticed this curious circumstance, despite its obviousness.

Here are several examples of such surprising anticipations:

- The oxygen that all animals breathe now on Earth did not exist originally. It was produced along 2000 million years by blue algae / cyanobacteria, supposedly because this was beneficial for them at these times, with oxygen produced as a residue of their photosynthesis. Curiously, oxygen was later essential for the existence of all animals.
- Whether the first cells already had, or not, the capacity of evolving much later into an enormous variety of types, including the possibility of aggregating into multicellular intelligent animals, they could not have developed this capacity by natural selection, because this selection is supposed to favor only the organisms best adapted to their current environment, so the capacity of evolving in the distant future not only has no survival value in the present, but should represent in principle an impediment. It seems obvious that this capacity of evolution is considerably more complicated, and therefore costly, than the capacity of merely generating identical copies of oneself.

- The eukaryotic cells of which all plants and animals are made appeared about 1000 million years before multicellular organisms even existed, and it is currently admitted, despite a notorious initial controversy finally settled by genetic evidence [19], that they did so as the result of the absorption of ancestral bacteria by ancestral cells of the class of archaea, in another example of traumatic event that surprisingly did not result in the disappearance of all its participants.

- The terrestrial plants that terrestrial animals would later need for their survival evolved before the appearance of these animals, supposedly as the result of the natural selection of the plants.

- The 4 limbs and 5 fingers that have been conserved in terrestrial vertebrates initially resulted from the multiplication of the tail of an aquatic worm-like animal (~ amphioxus or earlier, around > 500 million years ago?), in another example of likely disastrous event that nevertheless produced viable offspring. Of course there is no fossil evidence of this event, but some genes at the tips of the tail and fingers of vertebrates with a tail and four limbs are essentially identical.

- The feathers of birds appeared originally in dinosaurs, probably to keep them warm, and evolved later presumably to cushion falls from trees, later to allow gliding, and finally to allow flying.

- Additionally, there is some controversy about the timing of the appearance of the abstract reasoning and mathematical abilities of Homo sapiens, as compared to the time when these capabilities became truly beneficial, in organized agricultural societies. However, this point is complicated and will not be further discussed here.

2.6 Some clarifications about superhuman beings.

Since this article contains several references to superhuman beings, we will include here a few remarks intended to avoid possible misunderstandings. These remarks are based only on scientific considerations, intuitive logic and common sense, and are compatible in principle with all known serious religions.

- For all practical purposes, any reference to a superhuman being, or power, or animate system, does not and cannot presuppose whether this being is finite or infinite, alive or not, conscious or not. We have no scientific means to establish with reasonable certainty any of these aspects.

- If we believe that there may be finite beings with arbitrary levels of complexity, power or intelligence, then we must believe that the universe is infinite. As it has been already remarked, the appearance by pure chance of complex beings would require a time exponentially greater than their level of complexity. Therefore, the problem of the appearance of a certain being of certain complexity cannot be solved by postulating that it has been created by another finite being of greater complexity, because the same problem would affect the latter being. Instead, we must admit that the time dimension of the universe is infinite. As has been already remarked, "In an infinite time, everything that is possible will occur, and it will occur an infinite number of times".

- The belief that everything in the real world is finite is probably much less intuitively acceptable than that of the infiniteness of the universe. In the first case, if we progress along some possible dimension, such as space, time or scale, sooner or later we will find **nothing**, which seems rather shocking, if not outright incoherent, because by definition 'the nothing' does not exist. It seems more acceptable to assume that there is something wherever we go or look at, even if we cannot perceive it, and, inversely, to admit that the fact that we cannot perceive something does not prove that it does not exist.

2.7 Summary

In sum, there is a considerable amount of evidence in favor of the idea that no mind can design or build a machine even approaching its own intellectual capacities. In consequence, machines built by humans must never be allowed to make important decisions without the supervision of a human reasonably competent in the corresponding domain. In this respect, at present, the most generalized fear related to the future of AI is that at some point in the future these machines will take power and treat humans as slaves, or directly exterminate us, which has resulted in the idea of incorporating ethics or morality rules into these machines. However, as proved in the previous sections, the real danger of these machines does not, and will never lie in their potential lack of ethics, but in their inevitable and unpredictable tendency to commit enormous errors, including their foreseeable inability to interpret correctly even the most elementary ethical rules.

However, with the adequate supervision of competent humans, these machines can certainly be very useful in many domains, but they represent and will always represent a considerable danger for naive or vulnerable people, especially children and adolescents, who have the innate tendency to adopt what they see as models at face value without criticism, and even become emotionally attached to them, but also for adult people without enough competence in the corresponding domain, and / or with immature personalities or in difficult situations.

3. Consciousness and self-awareness

3.1 Introduction

The subject of consciousness, that is, self-awareness, the feeling of 'self', together with the associated phenomena of pleasure and pain, has been a part of human metaphysics since the mists of time, and since the last half of 20th century it has also become a matter of scientific study. However, in the scientific aspect only speculations are possible, because consciousness is essentially a subjective sensation and there exists no machine capable of detecting or measuring consciousness. In principle, at least it seems possible to assume that there can be no consciousness in inanimate objects, but even this is not evident, because there may be animation where we cannot perceive it. In consequence, no theory of consciousness can be scientifically proved, at least in the foreseeable future, so the theories proposed so far, and the one of this article is no exception, should be considered mere hypotheses. Nevertheless, the hypothesis proposed here happens to have testable consequences and also to provide answers to some important problems for which today's science has no real answers.

For our purposes, we will first propose as reference the book [20], because it gives a reasonably complete view of the subject within its concision, and also because, as far as the author knows, it is the proposal that most resembles that of this article. This book classifies the theories of consciousness proposed so far into the following categories:

A: All thinking is pure computation; in particular, feelings of conscious awareness are evoked merely by carrying out the appropriate computations.

B: Awareness is a feature of the brain's physical action; and, whereas any physical action can be simulated computationally, this simulation cannot by itself evoke awareness.

C: As B, but the physical action cannot even be simulated computationally.

D: Awareness cannot be explained by physical, computational, or any other scientific terms.

We can note that the category D includes the traditional religious views of consciousness, including the well-known duality body-soul. Even so, categories B and C are also compatible with religion, because in this respect the postulated physical phenomena are as compatible as all those that we already know. By contrast, it seems difficult to reconcile the category A not only with religious belief but also with science and logic, because information is not an objective reality, but a code that must be interpreted by a conscious mind. For example, a certain physical sequence of bits can mean different things depending on the computer language used to interpret them. However, if we interpret 'computation' mainly as a physical process, then the category A amounts to B or C.

The proposal of this article, like that of the abovementioned book, belongs to the category C. In short, it assumes that consciousness requires the interaction of two parts:

- The **sentient** part, a physical phenomenon not described by today's physics.

- The **computational** part, which includes the intelligence and memory necessary to understand and remember the sentient part.

These parts and their integration will be analyzed in the following sections.

3.2 *The sentient part: an unknown physical phenomenon.*

One of the reasons why most atheistic scientific theories of consciousness exclude the participation of an unknown physical phenomenon is most probably that today's accepted physical theories do not describe any phenomenon compatible with the generation of consciousness, other than pure computation. We will provide here a description of a possible such phenomenon, based on the existence of what has traditionally been called **ether**, which is not admitted by today's theories of Relativity, and is somewhat 'neutral' for Quantum theories, which postulate that space, or

vacuum, is not absolutely empty, but its behavior is essentially unpredictable. However, the hypothesis of the existence of ether has existed even before the invention of Relativity, it remains perfectly valid and still has considerable support [21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34]. This hypothesis is not accepted by today's mainstream physicists mainly because it would essentially invalidate Special and General Relativity, but several replacements for these theories based on the existence of ether have already been proposed.

In short, the ether, or aether, is a medium filling the entire space. All forms of matter and energy are simply particular features of the ether, which is why this medium will be called here preferentially **substrate**, or **substratum**, because the word 'ether' suggests something 'ethereal', which seems in contradiction with the real role of this medium, which is the basis or support of everything else we know. Our hypothesis is simply that the subjective part of consciousness is another **manifestation of the substrate**, like everything else we know. In addition, we postulate that the behavior of this medium is entirely deterministic, like General Relativity (GR) and its proposed replacements, although this requires adjustments in Quantum theories, as proposed in [20] or [34], which would have been inevitable anyway because it is well known that GR and Quantum theories are incompatible.

In more detail, we could propose a simple preliminary idea by a comparison of the mind with something like a coil spring. The effect of stimuli on the mind could be compared to the reversible deformation of the spring from its initial configuration under the effect of some force, and suffering would occur when the deformation of the spring approaches the limit of rupture or irreversible damage. However, this does not explain what pleasure is. Therefore, we will propose a more complex model: the activity of the mind consists in a variety of oscillations occurring inside groups of neurons; **pleasure** occurs when some external influence is **synchronized** with some internal oscillations and therefore tends to reinforce them, and **pain** occurs when the oscillations are **not synchronized**, causing tensions inside the neurons and interfering with their activity. This is compatible with the neural mechanisms of reinforcement discovered in real neurons and described in a previous section.

However, this proposal leaves an open question: although it is clear that sufficiently intense reinforcement stimuli can reinforce the activity of a neuron far beyond its current level, it is not clear whether there exist neural systems that cannot maintain indefinitely their activity without periodic reinforcement from outside. In principle, we can suppose either that real neural systems are not capable of maintaining indefinitely their activity without external reinforcement because they are intrinsically unable to do so, or that this happens because of the negative reinforcement of the physiological effort induced by this activity.

We can note that the mechanism proposed in [20] also includes a phenomenon unknown to current physics, namely a new form of quantum gravity, which supposedly takes place inside the microtubules of neurons. More precisely, in this book Mr. Penrose provides solid and detailed proofs of the incompatibility of current Quantum theories with General Relativity, and deduces the need for a replacement of the former by some new theory that he does not develop in detail. Our hypothesis shares these ideas, but it also shares the opinion of the many authors who think that Relativity also must be replaced by a theory based on the substrate, and it also postulates that the special physical phenomenon that underlies consciousness can occur not only in microtubules, but also in any part of the neuron that can be subject to interaction mechanisms or tensions of any kind, like for example cell membranes or walls.

3.3 The computational part

The computational part of the mind is easy to understand, because in this aspect the mind is essentially equivalent to a computer. However, in [20] it is stated that this computational part is not algorithmic. Our proposal is slightly different: this part really works like an algorithm, but, as explained in the section about the intelligence of AI, this algorithm is far too complex for humans to understand. Therefore, in practice the result is the same, there is just a difference of terminology.

This aspect of the computational mind can settle in principle the long-lasting controversy about free will. Many authors have claimed that humans cannot be considered to have real free will because their behavior will always be ultimately determined by their external environment. Furthermore, a reference experiment [35], which was later repeated and commented massively, seems to show that some unconscious neural activity always takes place before the subject experiences the corresponding conscious awareness. However, according to our proposal, this does not prove that this unconscious activity causes the conscious awareness, because this unconscious activity is the self-awareness itself. Therefore, we can consider that free will is effective, at least, against possible influences of the environment and of

other humans, because, as shown before, it is too complicated for other humans to understand or manipulate us. However, in principle, superhuman beings could understand, predict and even subtly manipulate our thoughts without us noticing anything abnormal.

In evolutionary terms, it seems clear that the computational part of consciousness is what implies the advantage of consciousness in terms of survival and adaptation to the environment. Most probably, the brains based on reinforcement mechanisms appeared in order to allow the possibility of learning complex strategies too voluminous to be included in the genome as innate strategies.

3.4 The combination of the two parts

We postulate that, in order to produce consciousness, the sentient and computational parts must be integrated, so that there is a correspondence and synchronism between them.

An immediate consequence of this postulate is that **machines like today's computers cannot be self-conscious**. There are at least the following reasons:

- In a computer simulating a neural network, the software neurons are processed sequentially, whereas in the brain they work simultaneously.
- Computers do not process information in the same form as neurons, that is, analogically. For example, for a computer, binary '10000000' is greater than '0111111', whereas physically, if the bit value '1' is represented by a higher value of an electrical magnitude than '0', then '0111111' will be more intense, and in any case no known computer architecture can reflect any complete physical correspondence or synchronism with the corresponding natural analogic neuronal network. In consequence, any self-conscious computer would have to be as massively parallel as the brain, which is essentially unthinkable with the technology of the foreseeable future.

On the other hand, our hypothesis implies that **the existence of consciousness is not an all-or-nothing phenomenon**. Depending on their intelligence, animals can be considered self-conscious to a degree roughly proportional to their intelligence. Furthermore, our hypothesis implies that a considerable number of animal species, most probably including all vertebrates, can experience pain and pleasure.

3.5 Practical consequences in human health and psychology

The above hypothesis has very important practical consequences in the domains of human health and psychology, most of which are already admitted by today's science but most often without understanding their ultimate causes.

The mechanisms of neural reinforcement are already well known, but their complete consequences do not seem to have been fully understood. For this purpose, we will consider a reference experiment [36, 37], which was later profusely repeated, reportedly even in humans. In this experiment, some rats were allowed to perform an electrical stimulation of a certain region of their brain by pressing a lever. The result was that these rats kept on pressing the lever obsessively without interruption, neglecting any other possible activity like food or sex, until they fell exhausted.

This experiment has a few extremely important consequences whose implications still do not seem to have been fully understood by mainstream scientists, perhaps because these consequences have been considered to affect only the problem of drug addiction:

- The occurrence of a reward creates or increases the impulse to perform the strategies that were active at the time of the reward, and the more intense the reward, the greater this impulse.
- A reward stronger than those having reinforced the useful strategies already stored in the memory of the individual will bypass these strategies and impose the strategies that were active at the time of the reward. This is the well-known phenomenon of **addiction**, and it can result from any sufficiently strong reward, not only those resulting from electrical stimulation of the brain or psychoactive illegal drugs.
- The only way to control or suppress the addictive impulse is by physical impossibility to perform the addictive behavior or by an equivalent negative reinforcement. Otherwise, the individual will keep on performing the addictive strategy unless one of these conditions is met.

We can also note that in general active behavior will not be a model of dignity or of usefulness for the survival and evolution of the individual or the society.

If we realize that the above category of rewards can potentially include any kind of reward clearly higher than the negative reinforcement resulting from the effort necessary to obtain this reward, we can easily understand why the following factors are essential for health, as already admitted by today's medical science:

- Physical exercise consuming an amount of energy in proportion to the physical abilities of the organism.
- Food requiring significant digestive work, that is, with enough vegetal fiber and not consisting mainly of purified, too easily digestible nutrients like pure sugar or ultra-processed fat or protein.
- Avoidance of any artificial form of reward of strength comparable or higher than that of natural ones.

Failure to respect these principles could result in the need to control the resulting addictive behavior by means of physiological efforts for which the organism is not well prepared, at least in a repetitive way, producing the following problems, whose ultimate cause is not well understood by today's medical science:

- Chronic inflammation, when the internal strategies active at the moment of the initial strong reward consisted in causing some kind of inflammation, however weak or trivial. This inflammation will be later multiplied until the pain it causes matches the intensity of the reward, with the potential of causing organic dysfunction and also premature cancers after some time. In this respect, we can note that inflammation is a natural phenomenon, but it is intended only to fight infections, because it interferes with the normal activity of the organs it affects. In consequence, in principle humans are not well prepared for chronic inflammation, which can be expected to result in poor performance and reduced lifespan.
- Autoimmune diseases, when the strategies active at the moment of the initial reward included some immune attack, however weak or trivial, against some pathogen. The immune attack could be later directed against some organ of the individual either because of some cross-immunity resulting from an accidental partial molecular resemblance between the pathogen and some cells of the organ, or merely for absence of any pathogen to attack.
- Many other diseases for which today's science knows no ultimate cause may also be the result of the positive reinforcement up to dangerous intensity levels of otherwise normal internal strategies of the organism.

The above considerations have somewhat unexpected consequences:

- Ultimately the physical damage caused by an addictive product will depend only on the total amount of psychoactive principle absorbed, because this is what the resulting physiological damage will match. For example, low-tar tobacco is not necessarily healthier than the classical variety, because its lower negative reinforcement will induce smokers to smoke more frequently, and former non-smokers to smoke. The same consideration applies to electronic cigarettes. By contrast, low-nicotine / same-tar variants would be presumably healthier than the classical variant, though not particularly good for the tobacco business.
- It is not clear whether sugar is bad for teeth because it feeds harmful bacteria inside the mouth or because it is a too easily digestible refined food. Most probably, both considerations apply.
- The relative compatibility of tobacco smoking with an acceptable mental performance results from the damage caused by tar and other irritants of tobacco, plus the inflammations induced by the action of nicotine on some nervous terminals. All this is possible only when the diet available to sedentary people is sufficiently rich to support intense physical activity.
- It is very difficult to extinguish an addiction by pure force of will, because the addiction bypasses the neural circuits that materialize free will. In contrast, it is usually much easier to extinguish the addiction by performing the addictive behavior without the psychoactive principle, because the neural centers responsible for the calculation of rewards, though rather strong, are not very clever. The suppression of the active principle can be made gradually, so as to avoid a brutal abstinence syndrome.

Less unexpectedly, another consequence of the above is that the systematic pursuit of intense pleasure leads nowhere, and certainly not to happiness. The initially intense pleasure is soon eroded by the discomfort resulting from

the inevitable associated physical effort or damage, so the victims always want more and more pleasure, while becoming increasingly sick. The futility of the pursuit of pleasure is known since the mists of time. Practically all religions and most philosophical systems prescribe moderation in the search for pleasure, but some doctrines or texts are more specific about to this precise subject. For example, Buddhism preaches the avoidance of suffering instead of the search for pleasure. The Gospel of Luke (6:20-26) blesses the poor, the hungry, the sad and the persecuted, and curses not only greed, vice, frivolity and arrogance, but directly everybody who enjoys more than enough riches, victuals, fun or flattery. Furthermore, an entire book of the Bible is mainly centered on this subject: Ecclesiastes [38] proclaims that immensely rich and powerful people are not happier than any modest manual worker. In more technical terms, we can say that if the average intensity of the rewards felt by the individual is higher than the normal or natural levels, the life of this individual will not be happier than normal, but just more intense for both good and bad, and also shorter in the same proportion, and it will probably not be much beneficial for the society.

3.6 What is there after death?

It is probably no exaggeration to remark that the fundamental reason of the interest of humans in the nature and mechanisms of consciousness has always been to try to understand what will happen to us after death. In consequence, the author of this article has felt obliged to include some sections on this subject. However, science cannot provide acceptable rigorous answers to these questions. Furthermore, this article is about consciousness, not identity. Therefore, for now, readers are invited to provide their own answers.

Do you have any religious belief? If yes, then your religion provides the answers.

Do you feel that you are the same person that you were yesterday? And one month ago? One year ago? Ten years ago? At age 20? 10? Depending on your answers, you can estimate the likeliness of resurrecting in the future according to a completely materialistic perspective.

Additionally, do you believe that the universe is infinite? In an infinite time, everything that is possible will happen, and it will happen an infinite number of times.

Some aspects of these questions will be further discussed later in this document when comparing our theory with today's most popular alternatives.

3.7 Summary

The main practical conclusions of our analysis of the mechanisms of consciousness, pleasure and pain are the following:

- In principle, we can assume that no electronic computer or artificial intelligence is likely to develop consciousness, or feel pleasure or pain, at least with the technologies of the foreseeable future.
- By contrast, whoever has some moral principles should be very much worried by the treatments that are inflicted by humans to animals, with priority given, of course, to the most intelligent ones when a choice is inevitable, but without neglecting the others in any way.
- With all the more reason, the preceding prescription should be applied also to any human activity involving the artificial creation or modification of even minimally intelligent biological organisms of whatever kind for whatever purpose, such as genetic manipulation or eugenics, manufacture of biological computers or other tools, etc. Activities of this kind would be not only morally repugnant, because of the risk of generating suffering, but profoundly stupid, because, as this document shows, the results would never match, let alone surpass, those of technologies based on inanimate objects.

4. Comparison with religious beliefs

4.1 General considerations

The arguments of most religious beliefs about consciousness and life after death are essentially as follows:

- a) There is a being or entity, or more than one, vastly or infinitely more intelligent and powerful than humans, that has or have taught us the fundamentals of these subjects, which our modest intellectual power is unable to understand by itself. To simplify and avoid excessive verbosity, in the rest of this discussion we will

call 'God', among these beings, the entity who ultimately makes the decisions, and assign to him, according to traditional usage, or arbitrarily if you prefer, the masculine grammatical gender.

- b) God has proved his power in the past to some privileged humans by means of astonishing actions, usually known as miracles, and these humans subsequently transmitted the teachings of God to many other humans.
- c) In addition to fundamental knowledge about the nature of the universe and its creatures, God has transmitted instructions about how humans should behave to enjoy life after physical death and avoid a variety of divine punishments during their biological life or its supernatural continuation.

Of course, the central point of this argumentation, and also its weakness, is b): if miracles really occurred as described in religious texts, then the only reasonable strategy for humans is to accept all the teachings of God at face value, but we cannot be completely sure that the miracles occurred as narrated in religious texts. It could also be objected that, even we accept that miracles were real, nothing proves that God is well-intentioned, but this objection does not seem reasonable. In principle, God may be either benevolent, indifferent or malevolent, but malevolence occurs, as far as we know, only in humans as the result of irrational impulses. It is not an intelligent strategy, as proves the fact that practically all creatures having survived so far avoid harming others unless it is required for their own survival. In consequence, in principle we can admit that malevolence is irrational and therefore God cannot be malevolent. He cannot be indifferent either, because in this case he would not have bothered selecting some humans as prophets and instructing them to preach religions.

According to the above, we will try to evaluate the historical evidence in favor of the hypothesis that the miracles at the origin of religions, at least of the major ones, were real facts. However, we will not make any hypothesis about the possible 'nature' or 'structure' of God: theological aspects are definitely out of the scope of this article, because they cannot be established according to objective facts, and anyway it is impossible for humans to understand the full, real nature or structure of God or even of the lower-rank superhuman entities (angels, etc.) who are or may have been in contact with humans at present or in the past. For our purposes, it suffices to postulate that these beings are incomparably superior to us and God is superior to all the others.

To begin with this subject, we can remark that, since it is undeniable that there are beings inferior to us, there is no reason to exclude the possibility of existence of beings superior to us, and even vastly or infinitely superior. Furthermore, it is also undeniable that these beings could perform miracles in ways indistinguishable from our idea of God. In consequence, mere common sense tells us that religious beliefs, far from being comparable to fantasies, superstitions, or delusions, are perfectly reasonable, and this view has been universally accepted by humans at least until a few centuries ago, when science and technology began accomplishing a variety of astonishing results which common people could no longer understand and regarded almost as 'magic'. The result has been an increasing tendency, obviously promoted by some scientists and philosophers in their own interest, to discredit religious beliefs as fantasies or superstitions, or, worse, mental troubles, despite the undeniable fact that they are at least as objectively reasonable, if not far more so, as the opinions of scientists about the origin of the universe, consciousness and soul, and so on. On the one hand, scientific knowledge, necessarily limited to specialized areas, cannot be legitimately extrapolated to other domains, and on the other hand no hypothesis about God, or even only consciousness and soul, can be confirmed or refuted experimentally in any scientifically legitimate way. Even worse, the denial of religions can only be the result of the belief that, thanks to their science, sooner or later humans will be the supreme beings of the universe, a belief that is not only catastrophically wrong from a scientific point of view, as explained in section 2, but can also lead to pathological megalomaniac tendencies potentially destructive for humankind.

Once these points have been established, we will analyze in further detail the historical evidence currently available in favor of the belief that most religions, if not all, had their origin in real miracles. For reasons of space, and also, why not admit it, of ignorance of the author, this analysis will be limited to two of the best-known examples: Judaism and Christianity, which are extensively documented and reasonably known to the author.

Our basic argumentation will consist in establishing that the appearance in a human society of a proper religious belief, not merely a legend, superstition, or minor sect, requires the occurrence of events far beyond the knowledge of the witnesses of these events. By contrast, the countless hoaxes, manipulations or hallucinations that have occurred along human history have had only minor or anecdotic consequences, without any possible comparison with the dramatic,

decisive influence of major religions on human history. Furthermore, our hypothesis is not invalidated by the fact that many tales of miracles contained in religious scriptures may not reflect real facts or are impossible to verify. We will not assume, in any way, that *all* the miracles described in ancient texts were real, because it suffices to show that only a few of them probably were, which was anyway more than sufficient to produce a dramatic or traumatic effect on their witnesses: readers are invited to imagine what impression they would feel if they happened to witness even only one real such event! Most of us would be scared to death in this situation! Furthermore, it is likely that the occurrence of just one such event can make its witnesses far more prone to accept tales about other miraculous achievements, supposedly performed by the same being(s), without verifying them directly.

The following analysis is complemented in section 5.3 by a review of the main arguments that have been adduced in recent times against the adequacy or even rationality of religious beliefs.

4.2 Contemporary appearance of religions: Cargo cults

An interesting example of this central idea can be found in the so-called **cargo cults**, which are religions that appeared in some remote islands of the Pacific where the primitive inhabitants first met reasonably benevolent foreign troops able to deploy 20th century technology and economic wealth [39]. These are probably the only cases in which the appearance of true religions has been satisfactorily documented, and they seem to confirm that a considerable technological superiority is necessary to induce the appearance of a true religion in humans. In this respect, we can remark for example that, when Europeans arrived in America in the 15th and 16th centuries, their technological superiority was not sufficient to induce true religious beliefs: they were considered just powerful humans, not gods. We can also observe that the existence of cargo cults has been extensively proclaimed by atheistic authors, more or less explicitly, as a proof or indication of the primitiveness of *all* religious beliefs, but in fact what the appearance of these cults prove is just the opposite, that is, that it would have taken at least the human technology of the 20th century to induce real religious beliefs in the people of the times of Moses or Jesus Christ.

4.3 Judaism

Although the Hebrew Bible and later Jewish religious texts contain many tales of miracles, we will assume that, according to our hypothesis, those occurred in the times of Moses were sufficient by themselves to produce the appearance of Jewish faith as understood nowadays. In this respect, we can remark that these texts also admit the existence of people or other beings endowed with the ability to perform magic, without necessarily respecting God's will or even with evil intentions, but somehow God inspires true believers to distinguish manifestations of divine power from those of evil creatures. This is clearly the case of the miracles performed by Moses, which have been always recognized as unmistakable manifestations of God's power.

In the Hebrew Bible, also called Old Testament by Christians, the Book of Exodus (3-17) describes a variety of miraculous events intended to allow the survival and reinforce the faith of the people of Israel: in Egypt, a staff becoming a snake, miraculous appearance and healing of leprosy, plus ten plagues (the Nile as blood, frogs, flies and gnats, cattle pests and rashes, hail, locusts, darkness and slaughter of first-borns); in the desert, several more miracles (division of the waters, provision of quails and manna, clean water from bitter liquid or from dry rock, etc.). Many contemporary authors have tried to find historical evidence not only for these miracles, but in general for all the events described in the Hebrew Bible. Here, we will propose [40] as a first reference, which can be further complemented by [41, 42, 43]. In principle, the fundamental conclusion of these works about the miracles described in the Book of Exodus is that most of them, namely the first nine plagues and the miracles of the desert, can be identified with natural but exceptional events, that is, they are materially possible but can have occurred precisely in their biblical environment only under the influence of a superhuman power. Of course, it is also possible to believe that these events occurred by pure chance or even did not occur at all, but this is improbable: it is highly unlikely that a whole human tribe or society could have accepted the authenticity of such a series of miraculous events if none had occurred at all. By contrast, the authenticity of other events also described in the Scriptures, such as the staff turning into a snake or the slaughter of first-borns, is far less evident, but, as explained before, the real occurrence of some of the abovementioned natural but exceptional events would have been more than sufficient to instill deep faith in practically any normal human, and it would also have added likeliness to miraculous events not witnessed directly but reported by other people.

4.4 Christianity

In the Christian canonical Scriptures, that is, the New Testament, there is a profusion of tales of miracles, but there is a big difference between them. On the one hand, with only one exception, they are attested only either in the Synoptic Gospels, the Gospel of John, and the Acts of the Apostles (we do not consider tales of miracles the visions of the author of the Apocalypse). If we consider, as seems reasonable, the double and triple traditions of the Synoptic Gospels as only one independent source [44], we find that each miracle is attested by only one independent canonical source, with the possible exceptions of some miracles appearing in both the Synoptics and John's Gospel, which represent two independent sources if we accept, which is somewhat dubious, that the author of this Gospel did not depend on the Synoptics for these miracles. By contrast, the Resurrection of Jesus is attested or at least recognized by all New Testament authors, and most especially by St. Paul, who in principle cannot have depended on the Greek Synoptics because, according to practically all experts, he wrote his Epistles many years before the redaction of the Greek versions of these Gospels and the Acts. Furthermore, it is striking that the authors of the New Testament, excepting the Evangelists, did not include in their books any miracle other than the Resurrection, which makes it very improbable that they could have depended on the Gospels for their information about this miracle. In addition, all the heresies derived from the Christian doctrine also admit the Resurrection of Christ in some form, directly or indirectly, although these heresies count only as a few independent sources, because only those that appeared in the first half of the 1st century AD can be considered independent from the canonical NT. In sum, according to the available historical evidence, the possibility that the Resurrection really occurred is considerably more likely than that of any other miracle reported in the New Testament or the apocryphal Christian-like literature. In this respect, the New Testament, accurate or not, is undeniably a piece of historical evidence, and is also undeniably the one of this time whose authenticity and age has been most thoroughly attested by experts: the oldest authentic complete manuscripts of the NT available today were written just three centuries after the events they report, and some fragments or partial copies of the NT, especially papyri, have been dated to less than a century after these events. This is far closer than for most other documents written around these times, the oldest authentic currently available copies of which were written in the Middle Ages. In consequence, we will focus our analysis on the Resurrection of Jesus, for which the available written evidence is far more extensive than for any other Christian miracle and probably also than for any miracle tale of whatever origin.

In this respect, our reference source is [45]. This book provides an extensive study of a profusion of legends or writings about revenants, phantoms, and the like, so as to compare them with the reports of the Resurrection of Jesus and find whether this event, according to the available evidence, can be considered unique and / or particularly likely, at least in comparison with the others. Readers unable or unwilling to study in detail the approximately 800 pages of this book can find a concise synthesis in the lectures [46, 47], or in works of other authors like [48], and an even more concise explanation could be as follows: the resurrection of Jesus is attested by a large variety of independent authors, most of whom did not report any other miracle, and seems to have produced a dramatic effect on its direct witnesses, resulting in the birth of a major religion which, 2000 years later, gathers more believers than any other. No other historical event of these times has so much documental support. The possible objection that the historical documents written by witnesses of the resurrection of Jesus were not impartial because their authors were Christians is absurd: obviously, people having witnessed an event like the resurrection of Jesus become automatically Christian by definition, independently from their previous degree of impartiality.

We will not try to determine here what happened exactly, beyond the fact that a large number of relatives, friends, disciples or acquaintances of Jesus sincerely believed that he had died, and shortly after they were able to see and touch him as any other live human. This event admits a merely materialistic hypothesis, that is, that Jesus was never completely dead but strongly looked like if he were, plus a variety of hypotheses directly involving superhuman influences, for example that some superhuman power, or powers, induced in the witnesses the irresistible belief that Jesus was completely dead when he was not, or resuscitated him with their superior abilities or technologies. The available evidence is far from sufficient to provide any hint about the validity of any such hypothesis.

As for the other miracles reported in Christian Scriptures, we will not analyze all of them in detail, but we can observe that at least some of them admit natural explanations. For example, the profusion of apparently miraculous cures performed by Jesus could have been simply the result of a medical knowledge exceptional in this time and place, possibly exaggerated in most cases by subsequent oral transmission. Another miracle, which is often referred to with mockery by aggressive atheists to show the supposed absurdity of Christian beliefs, surprisingly has an easy natural

good faith interpretation: Mary and Joseph could have successfully passed the ordeal described in [Numbers 5:11-31], which in principle does not seem a big deal. The belief that Mary remained virginal after the birth of Jesus is more difficult to explain in natural terms; some have hypothesized a cesarean section, but the Protoevangelium Jacobi [20:1-4] suggests another possibility: a midwife, while attempting to verify this fact, suffered an unexpected incident, perhaps a luxation or an immune reaction, harming her hand temporarily. As usual, this incident could have been exaggerated, with the result that after this event no other midwife was eager to take the risk of trying to verify by herself the virginity of Mary.

4.5 Natural but exceptional events

An intriguing aspect of the above study is that apparently all the reviewed miracles corresponded to natural but exceptional facts. It is unconceivable that this restriction could correspond to some limitation of the power of God: someone with enough power to influence at the highest level of detail human societies and their full environment, even in an apparently natural manner, would hardly have had any difficulty to cause strongly unnatural events, like, say, turning rocks into food in front of a lot of people, or producing Pantagruelic meals out of thin air. We will propose here a few hypotheses about the restriction of God's action to seemingly natural events:

- One reason may have been to respect as much as possible the free will of humans, because too explicit proofs of the power of God could have traumatized the witnesses and transformed them practically into automata focused exclusively in following to the letter whatever absurdity that could be remotely interpreted as an order of God. In principle, this has probably spared mostly people who did not directly witness the miracles, but even direct witnesses would probably have been much more traumatized if the miraculous events had been spectacularly unnatural. As for the reason why God wants to respect human free will, we can only speculate, but one possibility is just fairness, in application of the Golden Rule 'Treat others as you would want to be treated'.
- An even subtler reason could have been to draw the attention of impartial researchers to these specific events. Truly impartial researchers would have probably avoided any in-depth analysis of reported facts too likely to have been invented. As for the importance of the impartiality of authors, readers are left to judge by themselves.

4.6 Common points and differences among major religions

Another point that has been massively discussed both by believers and atheists is why God has induced or tolerated many different religions that often contradict one another. To try to elucidate this question, this section includes below a description of some points that are apparently identical or similar in all major religions, and other points that are clearly different. Please note that, in this section as well as in the rest of this document, we will not try to differentiate between what that God wants and what he merely tolerates, which is an inextricable problem for the human intellect. However, we remind the reader that in the previous section we have provided evidence that God respects human free will as much as logically or metaphysically possible.

All significant religions share these common points:

- A set of moral commandments based on the Golden Rule 'Treat others as you would want to be treated'. In this respect, there has been however a difference: some religions have unmistakably stated from the beginning that the GR should be applied to all humans, whereas this point seems to have been originally less clear in other religions, some interpretations of which apparently restrict the GR to those who believe in the same religion or, much worse, to the people of the same ethnic, sexual or other unfairly defined group. However, fortunately, in modern times respected representatives of all significant religions have agreed that the Golden Rule must be applied to all humans [49, 50]. As for the reasons why God inspired the GR to humans, the most likely one is that this was essential for our survival, as proves the fact that the only human societies that have survived in the long term are those with moral principles based on the GR. We can also observe that the GR is compatible in principle with self-defense, because this Rule entitles us to defend ourselves from aggressors as long as we accept that other people have the right to defend themselves if we attack them. Further analysis of the Golden Rule is provided in section 4.7.
- A variety of practical instructions most often considered ritual, which can be roughly divided into the following categories
 - Payments and gifts in favor of the supposed human representatives of God.

- Diverse actions that may have practical benefits and may have contributed to the survival of the human society many centuries or millennia before humans could be able to deduce these rules by themselves. For example, some rules of Judaism seem to have anticipated modern scientific knowledge about microbes and immunology by more than 3000 years.
- Other rituals that do not seem to be of any practical benefit other than allowing believers to show their faith to others, more or less in proportion to the effort necessary to perform these rituals.
- The assurance that there will be eternal life after death. The details may differ between religions, but all of them affirm that this life will be better for those who have respected the commandments of their religion before their death.

By contrast, speculations about the nature or structure of God are often rather different among the diverse religions and unfortunately they have traditionally been the major reason, or rather the pretext, for a profusion of at best bitter, sometimes violent and even barbarous conflicts between the different religions. This document, apart from establishing that God is infinitely powerful at least for all practical purposes, will not try to establish any other characteristic of God, including whether he is all-powerful, infinitely powerful, or 'only' unspeakably powerful, because such speculations are rigorously beyond the reach of the human intellect.

In addition to the above speculations about God, religions often differ about a variety of material points. For example, they may provide different versions of the creation of the universe, but these theories are criticized much more frequently by atheists than by people of other religions, on the basis that the religious versions are obviously incompatible with the currently available scientific evidence. However, these criticisms are ridiculous, because religious tales about the creation of the universe and its inhabitants were transmitted to humans several millennia ago. Then, what should God have transmitted instead to the people living, for example, in the times of Moses, more than 3000 years ago? Relativistic cosmology? In addition to the obvious fact that these people would not have understood a single word, and to the less obvious fact that this cosmology is not better than the corresponding religious tales even by the standards of 21st century science, as shown for example in section 2.5.1, it is easy to show that no human scientific theory can ever explain the origin of the universe or the life it contains, because this problem is, for all practical purposes, infinitely too complicated for the human mind, for the reasons explained in Section 2.

There are also some differences between the emotional profile that the different religions induce on their followers, but there are far greater differences between the emotions that people experience or allow in practice and those allowed by the religions. For example, Buddhism, Confucianism or Christianity preach charity, self-control, patience and humility, and do not tolerate hate or wrath under any circumstance. By contrast, other religions, while also preaching the above virtues, may allow hate or wrath under specific circumstances. However, this does not show any contradiction of God, but rather his knowledge of the weakness and wickedness of humans: in practice, virtually nobody feels hate or wrath in full agreement with the precepts of their religions, and Buddhists, Confucians and Christians are often not an exception.

4.7 The Golden Rule

The Golden Rule "**Treat others as you would want to be treated**", in some of its variants, is the fundamental basis of practically all extant moral systems, religious or not, ever developed and put into practice by human societies. It is closely related to the concept of **justice**, which is innate in humans and superior animals, and can be found essentially in the following forms:

- **Positive** form "Treat others as you would want to be treated" or **negative** form "Do **not** treat others as you would **not** want to be treated". Despite their apparent difference, these forms are essentially equivalent, because hardly anyone wants to be treated with indifference or be harmed by omissions of others.
- **Universal** "Treat **others** (i.e. all humans) as you would want to be treated" or **in-group** "Treat **your neighbour** as you would want to be treated". The difference between the two forms is abysmal and it is probably no exaggeration to affirm that the in-group variant is the chief culprit of all the atrocities committed by humans along their history. We can also note that the in-group variant is the minimal form of GR necessary for the survival of a human group: in the long term, all human societies that have ignored this rule have disappeared. In other words, there is no merit for any human society to apply just the in-group form of GR.
- The biblical precept "Love your neighbor" is essentially a stronger version of the in-group variant.

- The GR is implied by the first article of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of the UN: “All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights, are endowed with reason and conscience, and should act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood”.
- The Kantian ‘categorical imperative’ is essentially the GR formulated in pompous terms, but with an additional insufficiency or awkwardness: whereas the GR can be applied independently to any particular situation, not all the possible reactions to a particular situation can be reasonably generalized as a rule or ‘maxim’.
- We can also note that elementary justice requires the extension of the universal form of GR to all conscious beings, the possible difficulty being to determine which beings are really conscious when they cannot explain their feelings. This applies to humans affected by neurological problems, to superior animals, and potentially also to other forms of life so far unknown to us.

Despite its simplicity, the GR, at least when applied in good faith, is an astonishingly powerful moral basis valid for practically any situation. Some skeptics have put forward a variety of objections, but their validity is more than dubious:

- A typical recurring objection is that, say, if I am a homosexual, I may feel entitled to force or pressure others to have a homosexual relation with me because I would like them to do the same with me. This is fine as long as the other people also like homosexual relations, but not if I force or pressure others, because I would not like to be forced to have a sexual relation against my will, be it homosexual or of whatever nature.
- The preceding argument may be considered valid for sadomasochists, many of whom like to be brutalized or humiliated, but again this would be a gross simplification: all these people like to be treated only according to their own fantasies, which do not necessarily coincide with those of others, and most often establish strict limits that must be agreed with their partners, and certainly would not like being inflicted treatments incompatible with their fantasies, in qualitative or quantitative terms.
- Another objection refers to the punishment of criminals. In a first approach, the GR seems to prevent us from punishing criminals because we would not like to be punished in the same way. However, in fact honest authorities should accept being punished like criminals if they commit a crime; the GR only requires the punishment to be deserved and proportionate. Furthermore, if the misdeed can harm others, the GR applied to potential future victims requires that authorities prevent the criminal from causing further damage. However, if the misdeed cannot harm others, then the GR requires authorities to consider their own misdeeds: this was brilliantly proclaimed by Jesus Christ in the famous episode of the adulterous woman [John 8:1-11]: “Let him who is without sin among you be the first to cast a stone at her”.
- Others have proposed to replace the GR by the formula ‘Treat others as they would want to be treated’. However, this would be inappropriate because the expectations of others might be unreasonable. By contrast, the true GR works in both directions: it provides us with a reference about how we should treat others, but it also provides a reference about what we should reasonably expect from others, because we must treat them in the same way. The GR is about justice, not egoism.

Some applications of the GR are affected by subtleties that may seem difficult to solve, but even in these cases the GR is an invaluable reference:

- It may be difficult to put ourselves in the place of people or beings that are very different from us, and most especially if they are unable to express their feelings for whatever reason. However, it is reasonable to assume that at least in certain aspects all people are essentially similar: for example, it seems safe to assume that no one would like to be killed, hurt, robbed, cheated or humiliated. Therefore, at least a basic form of the GR is always possible, and beyond this basic form the utmost prudence is always highly advisable, and polite and tactful communication, when possible, will almost certainly help.
- Retrospective application: For example, a reasonable interpretation of the GR in relation to children would consist in treating them as we would want (now) to have been treated when we were children, not as children would want now to be treated. Similarly, the GR can be considered in good faith incompatible with voluntary abortion or even contraception, because none of us would want (now) to have been aborted or prevented from being conceived by our parents when this was possible. This is in accordance with the fact that societies where contraception and abortion are performed indiscriminately are doomed to extinction with mathematical certainty.

4.8 Conclusion

The review of the available documental historical evidence strongly suggests that all significant religions had their origin in certain events resulting from the action of a superhuman entity and considered 'miraculous' by their witnesses. In principle, the following observations apply to these events:

- The evidence in support of the hypothesis of the authenticity of these events cannot be considered conclusive but is certainly at least as solid as the evidence that has been adduced against this hypothesis.
- The miracles reviewed in this document were all natural but exceptional events, and it is their improbability which made them appear as miraculous.
- The above review does not imply that all the miracles reported by religious texts corresponded to real facts. In fact, for most of them, the available evidence is objectively weak and believing these miracles depends mostly on faith. By contrast, the authenticity of the miracles reviewed above is supported by solid evidence.
- Apparently, the nature and distribution of these miracles was optimized by the superhuman entity to achieve the maximum effect on human societies while respecting human free will as much as possible.

We have already seen in Section 2.5.1 that at least one of the following statements is necessarily true:

- Either: The appearance of life in the universe occurred by pure chance over a period of time exponentially or infinitely greater than the age of the universe estimated by today's relativistic cosmology, a.k.a. the 'Big Bang' theory.
- Or: Life appeared as the result of the action of some superhuman entity capable of influencing not only the biochemistry of life but also its geological, meteorological, cosmic and thermodynamic environment.

Now we have gone a step further and proposed that this entity, which we have called 'God', also influences macroscopic wildlife as well as human societies at the highest human level, which has conditioned the entire human history of all times. Some authors have suggested that all the events analyzed in the sections 2.5 and **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** could be the result of pure chance, but the combination of all these events would have been infinitely improbable. Others have hypothesized that these events did not occur in reality, but this proposal is in contradiction with the considerable amount of evidence reviewed in this document.

5. Comparison with other popular beliefs or hypotheses

5.1 Theories of consciousness proposed by scientists or philosophers

In the following sections, we will review the most conspicuous theories of consciousness that have been proposed by scientists or philosophers, including also their opinions about religions, which indirectly may also be considered theories about consciousness. Please note that we do not speak about 'scientific theories' of consciousness or religion, but of 'theories proposed by scientists', because there is nothing scientific in these theories, which cannot be proved or refuted by humans by means of experiments.

5.2 Theories of consciousness proper

Our reference for this subject will be a rather exhaustive enumeration of around 300 theories of consciousness published so far [51], with a brief description of each one and an attempt of classification into roughly a dozen groups. This work has been included here because it has recently surpassed the domain of purely academic literature with the publication of an article about it in a popular science magazine [52]. More recently, another popular science magazine has published another review of theories of consciousness [72, 73]. There have been many other attempts of classification of the different theories of consciousness published so far, according to a variety of other criteria, which as far as the author knows were not intended as popular science and will not be analyzed here in detail.

The first impression that these classifications give is that they are not sufficiently precise, let alone useful. One can observe for example that the classifications proposed by the different authors are most often very different, and that their criteria are difficult to understand. For example, in [51], it is difficult to understand the difference between panpsychism and monism, or why the theories based on quantum physics have their own group when quantum physics is as physical as any other branch of physics. Therefore, in principle the first impression of the occasional readers saturated by such classifications could likely be that nobody has a clear idea of what consciousness really is, and therefore that the best approach to this profusion of theories may be to ignore them. We will not try to elucidate here whether the inclusion of the religious proposals in a small group of the first classification was a good faith decision or

an intentional attempt to undermine the popularity of religious beliefs by putting them on a par with a profusion of far-fetched proposals impossible to validate scientifically. However, it is necessary to warn that such an attempt could be very dangerous, because among this profusion of theories impossible to prove scientifically, religions are the only ones that include the moral principles necessary for the viability of any human society.

Additionally, a deeper analysis confirms that there is a considerable overlap between all these supposedly different theories, so that each one can be considered to represent only a small part of the full mechanism of consciousness, which, as explained in section 3, is far too complicated for the human mind to understand in scientific terms. However, this does not apply to religious descriptions, which renounce to the possibility of scientific validation (possibility which anyway does not exist for this domain of knowledge, because consciousness is a subjective phenomenon) in order to provide descriptions that any human can understand, while respecting as much as possible the real aspects of phenomena inaccessible to human science such as consciousness or soul.

Anyway, a fatal flaw of all the supposedly scientific theories listed in the above reference document is that, with one exception, they do not explain the sensations of pleasure and pain that underlie emotional phenomena. This suffices to invalidate them all, because pleasure and pain are fundamental and inseparable aspects of what we understand as self or consciousness.

5.3 Theories against religions

In this domain, probably the most conspicuous reference is the book of Richard Dawkins “The God delusion” [53], which can deservedly be considered a compendium of the innumerable writings that have been produced against religions at least in modern times. We will also review the main opinions of Sam Harris [54, 55], another one of the so-called ‘new atheists’, because apparently he proposes the replacement of religions by a frightening invasive or compulsory application of supposedly advanced technologies, fortunately still not developed, which strongly remind notorious dystopias like Huxley’s “Brave New World” or Orwell’s “1984”.

In this respect, a first analysis shows the following:

- One of the main arguments against religious beliefs is their supposed absurdity or irrationality in comparison with other forms of knowledge such as science, as understood nowadays, or common practical experience. However, we will show below that this supposed absurdity or irrationality is far trickier to prove than it could seem at first sight, and that it can also affect beliefs of other domains such as modern science.
- The biological arguments adduced by these authors have already been scientifically destroyed in the section 2.5 of this document.
- It has been adduced that the creation of the universe by some being instead of by pure chance does not solve the problem because in turn this being must have appeared either by pure chance or as the result of the action of an even more improbable being. However, this argument cannot be applied to infinite beings, and the portrait of God provided by major religions strongly corresponds to the scientific concept of infinity. The fact that this property can be evaluated scientifically only in mathematical theories but not by experiments is fully consistent with the claim of religions about the inaccessibility of God to the human intellect.
- The argument consisting in providing specific examples of supposedly religious people behaving badly or even criminally is unacceptably biased and ignores human weakness and free will. Average humans are subject not only to the commandments of their religions but also to the constraints of their environment. Therefore, it is normal that even true believers living in problematic environments could be tempted to commit a variety of antisocial actions or even crimes in order to ease their situation. By contrast, a fair analysis of the possible influence of religion on the morality of people should consist in comparing the morality of believers and agnostics in similar circumstances. A more detailed discussion on this subject is given below.

In the rest of this section, the above reference books will be referred to as ‘GL’ [53], ‘EF’ [54], and ‘ML’ [55].

5.3.1 The nature and basis of beliefs. Common sense

It has often been remarked that the ‘new atheists’ present a caricature of religious belief consisting in holding religious dogma as absolute immutable truth regardless of any possible evidence of the contrary. However, we have already

seen in section 4, and we will explain here in more detail, that in fact religious beliefs have no less support of evidence than practically any other belief of similar complexity and whatever kind.

As far as the author knows or remembers, the opinion of Mr. Dawkins on this subject just amounts to the abovementioned caricature, that is, religious belief is based on no 'evidence' at all, whereas scientific belief is based on 'evidence', and when 'evidence' changes thanks to technological advances, scientists have no problem to modify their views. A first obvious problem of this view, as any real scientist knows, is that scientific 'evidence' is often not so evident, which may induce scientists to propose or adopt, most often under the effect of external pressures or their own pride, very questionable views or strategies in the name of science. By contrast, Mr. Harris performs a rather exhaustive analysis of the concept of belief, some questionable aspects of which are detailed below, including for example the ubiquity of the concept of reason.

For our purpose, our first basis will be the mechanism of representation of concepts in superior brains sketched in the previous section 2.1.2. This mechanism can provide reasonable intuitive answers in practically all situations of life, including those in which some events cannot be predicted with certainty. By contrast, pure reason, as already remarked by Kant in his Critique of Pure Reason, an arch-famous book even though very few people seem to have read it, let alone understand it, and in simpler terms by neurologist Antonio Damasio [56], is not self-sufficient and is grossly inappropriate in situations of uncertainty. Reason, at least as viewed by Mr. Harris, allows only for the following degrees of certainty: true, false, or 'undecidable' [ML, ch 3, p 157]. This makes it inappropriate to manage uncertainty, for which purpose our brain has an innate system capable of estimating intuitively the likeliness of any possible event on the basis of past experience. Most probably, this likeliness is represented inside the brain by a continuous magnitude, but simple introspection shows that our innate scale of likeliness contains at least the following degrees:

- Certain
- Very likely
- Likely
- Fifty-fifty
- Unlikely
- Very unlikely
- Totally incredible

Furthermore, the brain is innately capable of combining the different values of likeliness estimated for many potentially significant events to produce a unified intuitive global evaluation of a context resulting in practice in a reasonably appropriate decision. This capacity is essentially what is usually known as **common sense**. By contrast, reason by itself is unable to predict properly a large part of the events of everyday life. For example, if you plant a seed on earth in certain conditions, a plant will grow, but you cannot reason this, it just happens. If somebody tells you something, you need past knowledge of the behavior of this person to decide whether you should believe this person or not, you cannot reason it as if this person were some kind of algorithmic automaton. Despite the common etymology, being reasonable, which amounts essentially to apply common sense, is very different from trying to apply reason, that is, logic, to every problem of everyday life.

In this view, a fanatic or fundamentalist would be someone who assigns to some matters a degree of absolute certainty acquired despite the evidence of past or present experience. Even so, things are still not so simple. Certainty is normal in many cases: for example, if you see a dog in front of you, it is normal to be certain of it, you are not a fanatic, unless, of course, you see a dog where there are no dogs, in which case you are still not a fanatic, but a sick person, unless, of course, you are dreaming, in which case it will be reasonable to suspect that you have a problem only if you do not remember later the scene as part of a dream but as a real scene, and even so this problem might be only momentary, for example transitory lack of sleep. By contrast, in complicated matters absolute certainty is not normal, and this affects both religion and science. Furthermore, even a superficial analysis shows that what determines the possible abnormality of a certain belief is the frequency with which it is confirmed by facts. In this respect, it is true that the miraculous events narrated by religious traditions are rather exceptional, but so are also other events that seem to us more physical, such as, say, St Elmo's fire, will-o'-the-wisp, or lightning fireballs, which few of us have ever seen but in general are not considered miraculous. Not to mention other legendary beliefs such as UFOs or Bigfoot. In all these cases, the corresponding beliefs cannot be considered a sign of irrationality, let alone of insanity, if they are believed also by a significant number of people, and religious beliefs certainly fulfil this condition. This is why reference

psychiatric manuals like the DSM explicitly exclude religious beliefs as a possible sign of mental trouble. By contrast, some common beliefs propagated by today's science are far stranger and incoherent than any religious belief. For example, the curvature of time, an essential feature of General Relativity, is an absurdity under any reasonable point of view; it can be defended only as a mathematical technique used to predict some experimental results. The mere existence of space-time itself as a real physical object is another absurdity: such thing cannot exist, because the part with $t > t_{\text{present}}$ still does not exist, and the part with $t < t_{\text{present}}$ no longer exists, so only the existence of the part with $t = t_{\text{present}}$ can be accepted as real. So, again, this thing cannot be a real physical object, but just a mathematical tool. In Quantum Mechanics, the situation is not better: in this theory, there exists an object called wavefunction, of whose physical existence no one is quite sure, and which has the miraculous properties of being able to fill the entire universe and of disappearing instantaneously over the entire universe also. This theory also postulates, among other similarly weird hypotheses, the existence of some miraculous mechanism that can reproduce the full results of the mathematical theory of probabilities without any underlying deterministic phenomenon. Furthermore, quantum physicists claim that this mechanism is capable of producing *perfectly random* events, which is not only physically impossible but scientifically meaningless, because the only possible definition of perfect randomness is that there is no underlying deterministic mechanism, which is impossible to prove scientifically: it is just possible to prove that we are unable to detect it. As for the possibility of a non-deterministic mechanism, if we admit it then our entire vision of the world collapses, because our mental schemas are not prepared to deal with events without cause, the only one that we can accept being the existence of God, which anyway we can accept but not understand. In sum, some of the aspects of physical theories admitted almost unanimously by today's physicists are at least as strange as, say, a virgin who has children, a man who resuscitates, or a being who can see everything.

Curiously, Mr. Harris at some point agrees that belief can be quantitatively uncertain, and even uses the terms 'spectrum' and 'gradation', but he does so only once, in [ML ch 3, p 151]. The problem is that this book was published in 2010, whereas in his 2004 book "The end of faith" the chapter about belief is built on the assumption that a belief can consist only in thinking that something is true or false, without any consideration of likeliness [EF ch 2, p 51], and in the rest of the 2010 book belief is treated as the consideration that some proposition is true, false or 'uncertain', without distinction of the degree of certainty [ML ch 3, p 157]. One strongly misses the use of the word 'opinion', which is precisely an uncertain belief, and, for this kind of belief, instead of the imprecise verb 'believe', as in 'I believe that God exists', one misses, if not the verb 'opine', which nobody uses, at least more precise expressions, like 'In my opinion, God exists', 'I believe that God probably exists', 'I think that God almost certainly exists', etc. Not doing so is the hallmark of non-scientific minds: if science is not precise in everything, it is no longer science. Even Mr. Dawkins routinely makes claims complemented by a likeliness estimate, as in "Why there almost certainly is no God", and he nominally distinguishes fundamentalists from common believers [GD ch 8.1], but unfortunately, in another example of his usual doublethink, this distinction is not made explicitly anywhere else, otherwise he should have called his book "The fundamentalist delusion" instead of "The God delusion", but then, most probably, he would have sold in total about one or two copies of his book, perhaps less.

On the other hand, Mr. Harris admits that a usual and legitimate form of acquiring knowledge is because others have told us so [EF ch 2, p 73]. The problem of likeliness is therefore transferred to the estimated reliability of the sources that provide us the indirect experience. And the problem of Mr. Harris' explanation is that his examples are far too simplistic. In present times, even the news presented by journalists of big serious corporations sometimes cannot be relied upon. As for facts supposedly established scientifically, there is no full guarantee either, most often because of the proliferation of mere mistakes in the interpretation of complicated experiments, but also because of external pressures for financial or political reasons, personal ambition of the scientists or a mixture of all that. We all can remember notorious sinister applications of supposed scientific evidence: for example, heroin was originally marketed as a non-addictive (!) replacement for morphine, the inventor of lobotomy received the Nobel prize, thalidomide was intended as an innocuous painkiller, sugar and tobacco were proclaimed for decades by the scientific establishment not only as free from harmful effects but sometimes even as good for health, and more recently respected doctors and pharmaceutical companies have caused a disastrous epidemic of opioid addiction that has caused hundreds of thousands of premature deaths and is still ongoing [57]. In particular, today's science has repeatedly proved unable to deal properly with human psychology and most especially with addictions.

By contrast, religious beliefs are supported by a considerable literature traceable to historic times and more abundant and reliable than any other known historic source, plus the opinion of a large part, if not the majority, of today's human

population. The insinuation of Mr. Harris that someone can believe the Christian doctrine just because the Pope says so, or because the Bible says so, is childishly simplistic: the real support of this belief includes the opinions of hundreds of millions of believers worldwide and of thousands of experts who have studied thousands of ancient documents to produce a reasonably unified version of the original biblical teachings. We have also shown that the miracles reported by the Jewish and Christian Scriptures cannot be objectively considered stranger or weirder than many widespread beliefs proclaimed by today's science. Most probably, the problem, but also the importance, greatness and merit of religious beliefs is that, unlike the absurdities shown above in the domains of science and popular beliefs, they have **moral implications**.

As a complement and illustration of the above considerations, several questionable points of Mr. Harris' discussion are studied below in more detail.

[EF ch 2, p 57]: "If perfect coherence is to be had, each new belief must be checked against all others, and any combination thereof, for logical contradiction...", which, according to Mr. Harris, would make it impossible to store coherently in one brain even only about 300 different beliefs. However, on the first hand, not all combinations of stored beliefs must be checked, but only those linked to the new belief by a chain of stored beliefs linked by pairs by a common concept. This produces a heavily pruned exploration tree, resulting in a drastic reduction of the exploration time. On the other hand, relations between concepts, or at least between the most significant ones, are stored in the brain so that they can be recovered almost instantaneously. The result is that, in practice, the number of beliefs that can be stored in a normal brain without contradiction is several orders of magnitude greater than 300. It is true, however, that the brain has a limited storage capacity, but in practice this limit appears only in artificially complex problems mainly in the domain of mathematics, but unfortunately also in many of today's legal systems, which have become so complex that they will soon be impossible to manage even with the help of computers, because these machines are unable to reproduce many of the concepts that the human brain can manipulate intuitively and innately.

Anyway, even if the claim of Mr. Harris were accurate, one does not easily understand the purpose of its inclusion in his analysis of the concept of belief. Does he imply that his beliefs are somehow exempted from this exponential limit, perhaps because they are derived supposedly only from the application of 'reason'? In fact, it is the contrary that happens, because the problem of finding historical evidence showing the influence of an overwhelmingly powerful being is far simpler than that of predicting the influence of some system of ideas, religious or not, on human societies, especially in modern times. Mr. Harris apparently does not realize that, just because 'errare humanum est', he himself can be wrong when he thinks that there exists some "type" of reason supposedly immune to errors. In fact, this "type" exists, but it is not what Mr. Harris thinks: it comprises only very elementary propositions with just a few logical terms, which anybody can understand, for example "if something is true, it cannot be false", etc.

[EF ch 2, p 67]: "... even the Holocaust did not lead most Jews to doubt the existence of an omnipotent and benevolent God...". Mr. Harris presents that as a proof of fanaticism, fundamentalism or caricatural faith, which is not realistic, because the Nazis were just wicked humans making a criminal use of the free will granted by God to everybody. By contrast, if the Nazis had been able, say, to split the waters of the English Channel to invade Great Britain, or to make fire rain from heaven to destroy London like Sodom and Gomorrah, the effect on the religious faith, not only of the Jews but of practically anybody else, would have been otherwise considerable. Curiously, a comparable effect really happened over Hiroshima and Nagasaki, but the Americans never pretended it to be a manifestation of God's wrath, let alone to be themselves comparable to God in any way. Furthermore, in another example of catastrophic context, the impotence of the religious authorities to remedy the Black Death plague of 1348 really did affect the religious faith of many people, resulting, at least according to many authors, in the shift from strict religious doctrine to the more mundane and hedonic system of values that was the hallmark of Renaissance.

[ML ch 1, p 67]: "... the level of humility of scientific discourse is, in fact, one of its most striking characteristics". This is essentially true, and this is the reason why most scientists abstain from writing offensive pamphlets against the good faith beliefs of a large part of the citizens of their societies. All truly experienced scientists know that their views and conclusions are always subject to possible errors, so most of them consider that science and religion are not in contradiction and can coexist as different domains of knowledge, as expressed by S. J. Gould through his idea of Non Overlapping Magisteria (NOMA). By contrast, Mr. Dawkins seems to abhor this idea [GD 2.5, p 77-85], considering that science really has something to say in the domain of religion, which is certainly not a humble position. As already explained in previous sections, the main idea of this document is, in agreement with NOMA, that the domain of science

comprises all the beliefs that it is possible to verify with almost absolute certainty, and its hard core is the domain of technology, in which theories are necessarily verified by the inexorable condition that any apparatus designed according to scientific theories must work properly according to its theoretical specifications. By contrast, religion includes the domains of knowledge that, on the one hand, are too complicated for science and technology, and on the other hand have moral implications, the latter condition being necessary to exclude from the domain of religion all inextricable scientific problems that are irrelevant from a human point of view. Mr. Dawkins, unlike many other scientists, opposes this idea [58] but, as expected, he does not seem to have any practical experience in applied science, he is just a polemist. As for Mr. Harris, he is not even a true scientist: he reportedly graduated as a neurologist at age 42, having being until this age a pure philosopher and already a well-known polemist, curiously with some penchant for Buddhism [59], so he can hardly be expected to have a real idea, let alone experience, of the true reliability of the ideas proclaimed by today's scientists, and most especially of theoretical ones. However, at least he admits that, unlike him, most scientists are genuinely humble people.

It is true, however, that, while there will always be a frontier between science and religion, this frontier can move in accordance to technological progress, by including in the domain of science some points that were previously in the domain of religion, but, as explained in the previous sections and in particular in sec. 2, there are absolute limits that human science will be never be able to surpass and therefore will always remain exclusive of religion.

[ML ch 3 p 164-170] "We have long known, principally through the neurological work of Antonio Damasio and his colleagues, that certain types of reasoning are inseparable from emotion [note with refs., esp. Damasio "The feeling of what happens"]. (...) The neurologist Robert Burton agrees that the 'feeling of knowing' (i.e. the conviction that one's judgement is correct) is a primary positive emotion that often floats free of rational processes and can occasionally become wholly detached from logical or sensory evidence [note with ref. to Burton "On being certain..."]. (...) [Quote of neurologist Chris Fritz with the same idea] (...) dopamine receptor genes may play a role in religious belief as well. (Follows a discussion about the effect of the D4 dopamine receptor gene and the drug L-Dopa)"

In support of this idea, Mr. Burton mentions examples of mental troubles that can produce pathological certainty or uncertainty. Mr. Harris also quotes papers showing that people with a particularly active form of the D4 receptor or given the dopamine agonist drug L-dopa are more likely than average to experience abnormal levels of certainty.

The idea that a proper emotional substrate is a precondition for correct reasoning, and therefore that reasoning can be affected by emotional dysfunctions, is commonly accepted by all neurologists, at least since the pioneering work of Antonio Damasio [56]. The central importance of the emotional system for all human mental activities is a consequence of the unconscious integration of all the knowledge available in the brain into the dopaminergic system, as explained at the beginning of this section. The integration of knowledge with emotions is necessary because this is the root of **motivation**, which, as we all know, is based on **pleasure** and **suffering**. The problem of Mr. Harris is, as the above quote shows, that he seems to believe that this emotional dependence affects only religious believers or mentally sick people, but apparently not himself or his atheistic fellows. Therefore, apart from his possibly malevolent and offensive comparison between religious believers and mentally sick people, Mr. Harris is simply wrong when he feels free from this bias just because his mental processes are based supposedly on 'reason', which, as we have already seen, is yet another innate and intuitive form of acquiring knowledge that is as prone to errors as any other and whose conclusions must necessarily be weighed against those of common sense and experience to produce truly reasonable decisions. This is essentially what Mr. Damasio called "Descartes' error": to believe that reason reigns supreme in all human mental processes. Therefore, it seems odd that Mr. Harris quotes this neurologist, unless he thinks that 'his' (Mr. Harris') kind of reason is somehow exempt from this rule, for some abstruse motive that he does not explain. Is this what Mr. Harris means by "certain types of reasoning", that is, that Mr. Harris' "type" of reason is the only good one, and that of others is not valid, especially if they believe in God? This is just a petitio principii: Mr. Harris proves nothing, he just presupposes arbitrarily that those who believe in God cannot reason appropriately, but that he himself can. On the other hand, we do not know whether Mr. Harris has had his own D4 receptor gene tested, which he should have done for the sake of rationality and impartiality, but we all must be aware that the balance of the dopaminergic system, and therefore of the equanimity of people, can also be deeply altered by some agents that have become far too common in our affluent societies: **psychoactive drugs**. Too many people still believe that the effect of these drugs, legal or not, is just limited to the pleasure / pain balance, but unfortunately they also have the effect of inducing an irrational sensation of certainty, of being in possession of the absolute truth. Furthermore, even natural but unjustified

forms of pleasure, such as eating more than necessary or indulging in indiscriminate sex, can affect the validity of mental processes because they influence the dopaminergic system, although it is also true that it is difficult to indulge in natural but excessive forms of pleasure without the 'help' of some psychoactive drug.

In sum, in the above passage Mr. Harris has raised an extremely important question for all humans and most probably for all finite conscious beings: **Humility is unpleasant, but arrogance is suicidal and potentially criminal.** However, it seems that Mr. Harris has not been able to transmit the impression of practicing what he preaches and applying his own considerations to his own mental processes. Unfortunately for him and his fellows, this requires, if only for chemical reasons, a great deal of hedonic austerity, which has not been traditionally the hallmark of atheists, but rather of religious people.

5.3.2 *Reliability of religious Scriptures*

[ML p 307, note 82] "Bible scholars agree that the earliest Gospels were written decades after the life of Jesus. We do not have the original texts of any of the Gospels. What we have are copies of copies of copies of ancient Greek manuscripts that differ from one another in literally thousands of places. Many show signs of later interpolation (...) scripture that is now deemed to be both mistaken and incomplete by the faithful (...) such a haphazard (...) seems a poor basis to believe that the miracles of Jesus actually occurred."

Apart from the subjective value judgements, all that is literally true, and has been adduced ad nauseam by the detractors of religion, but the conclusions that can be drawn from that are just the opposite of those of Mr. Harris and his fellows, because for the New Testament the situation is in fact far more favorable than for any other historical documentation:

- "The earliest Gospels were written decades after the life of Jesus": Possibly true, except for the now lost Hebrew version of Matthew's Gospel, which has been partially conserved in quotes from later authors. Anyway, this reflects a situation far better than for most other historical documents, often written decades or even centuries after the facts they describe.
- "We do not have the original texts of any of the Gospels": True, but we do not have the original copy of any document of this time either, except brief inscriptions carved on stone in monuments or included in mosaics.
- "What we have are copies of copies of copies of ancient Greek manuscripts that differ from one another in literally thousands of places": True, but for all other historical documents the situation is even worse: we have far more ancient copies of the NT than of any other historical document, and many of them were written around the 4th – 5th centuries BC, whereas most of the rest of our historical documents referring to these times were written in medieval times. Furthermore, an overwhelming number of the differences between extant copies of the same original NT document are irrelevant, most do not change the meaning or introduce only irrelevant changes.
- "Many [copies] show signs of later interpolation": True, but the profusion of available documents makes it easy to detect later interpolations and to reconstruct the original text common to extant versions.

Readers can verify by themselves, for example, that the oldest manuscripts that we conserve for the works or biographies of classical Greek philosophers like Plato or Aristotle, or other first-rank authors of these times, were written typically in the 9th – 10th centuries AD, and that the available manuscripts are a couple of orders of magnitude less numerous than for the NT. For lower-rank authors, things are even worse, and for works written about 3000 years ago we often do not know for sure even whether their supposed authors existed at all. All that can be easily verified on the Internet, especially through the Wikipedia, and also in modern editions of these works, which usually contain a list of the sources used to prepare the text, plus abundant notes about the variants. However, for the Bible, because of the considerable volume of this critical apparatus, it is usually omitted or shortened in popular editions, but it is available in full to the general public in more specialized editions, on paper or online.

In sum, the idea that the New Testament and most other religious scriptures should be considered largely unreliable is wrong and can result only from a vast ignorance of the reality of the science of History. Far from being the creation of a bunch of crooks and illuminati, religious Scriptures as available today are the result of the thorough work of hundreds or thousands of very competent specialists, who, even for the NT only, must at least master biblical Hebrew, classical and koine Greek, and Latin, together with an in-depth knowledge of hundreds of documents of these times and later, from inside and outside the Bible, plus the studies of their colleagues. In addition, they need the

collaboration of a variety of specialists in other languages such as Aramaic / Syriac, Coptic or Arabic, also archeology, and auxiliary related technologies.

To illustrate the real nature of the work of Bible scholars and also for the intrinsic interest of the corresponding subjects, we include below a few examples of controversial biblical points and their possible solution based on documental evidence.

Lectio difficilior

Paradoxically, one of the main arguments in favor of the authenticity of many of the biblical documents available to us is that they are too strange to have been faked. This does not mean of course that all strange writings must automatically be considered authentic, but that when someone fakes a document he always tries to make it as coherent and convincing as possible in order to avoid suspicions. Therefore, in principle, fakes can be detected when they contain only incoherences or oddities that are not too easy to detect but difficult to explain as good faith mistakes. Of course, this general rule does not exempt scholars from examining old texts with maximum detail before drawing conclusions. It is true that most of the Biblical books that have always been considered canonical contain significant incoherences or oddities that probably no true fake would have contained, but these incoherences have been exhaustively analyzed by the scholars of all ages with the conclusion that they did not seem to be, in general, signs of fraud, but mostly of comprehensible human errors. By contrast, documents that contain obvious oddities but also signs of tendentiousness were soon excluded from the biblical canon. Even so, some of them show signs of containing, in addition to clearly tendentious content, some fragments that seem to be traceable even to authentic words of Jesus, because they are reproduced in other sources, including some canonical ones, without evidence that they were copied from these more reliable sources. Therefore, these documents can be considered at least documents of interest for the analysis of the variants of the canonical ones, and the best known are the (Gnostic) Gospel of Thomas, the Gospel of Peter, and the so-called Protoevangelium Jacobi. Another, though less strange, document of interest in this sense is the Didache, which reproduces a large part of the precepts of Matthew's Gospel and does not seem directly derived from this Gospel, but rather from an older source common to both documents.

The Protoevangelium contains some tales about the early childhood of Jesus that are sometimes reproduced in Matthew's Gospel, sometimes in Luke's, and sometimes in neither. For example, Matthew and Luke omit the passages about Mary's parents and essentially also those about Zacharias, and Luke also omits the story of the Magi, that of the midwives, and the travel to Egypt. The Protoevangelium contains a good number of oddities: for example, Reuben and Salome are introduced suddenly without specifying who they are, and the passage [18:2] changes abruptly to first person to introduce a surreal scene that has little sense in this place and probably anywhere else. Because of all these oddities, it remains difficult to establish which was the ultimate source of each of the passages common to at least two of these documents, but sometimes the problem can be interesting, as shown later for the passage about the shepherds.

A comprehensive study of the plethora of manuscripts available today for the New Testament and for religious Scriptures in general shows that, for their authors, translators and copyists, the authority of their sources seems to have been far more important than their apparent coherence. Even so, sometimes these scholars introduced changes, either involuntarily because of mere mistakes, or voluntarily because the strange original readings could be considered suspect according to rules or other sources deemed at least as authoritative as the text on which they were working. This soon led scholars to the apparently paradoxical principle of *lectio difficilior*: if you have two different readings in different versions of the same document, then all other things being equal the most probable original text is the strangest one, because copyists and translators tend to adopt, consciously or by mistake, the readings that best fit the common knowledge or rules of their cultural environment.

The Synoptic problem and the two-source theory:

As the reader probably knows, the Gospels of Matthew, Mark and Luke show evident signs of having been copied or translated, at least in part, from a common written source. Until the 19th century, the traditional and unanimous explanation of this fact was that Matthew the Apostle first wrote his Gospel in Hebrew (or at least in Hebraic characters), then Mark wrote his own Gospel, followed by Luke. Today's Greek Gospel of Matthew is just a translation of the original Hebrew Gospel. However, in the 19th century, Protestant scholars produced the theory that in fact Mark's Gospel was the first one, and later someone used Mark's Gospel plus an anonymous Greek written source they

called 'Q' to produce the Greek document known today as Matthew's Gospel; later, or independently, Luke used Mark's Gospel, Q and a third source L to produce his own Gospel.

Although this theory is accepted nowadays by a significant proportion of specialists, it has two enormous problems:

- There is nowhere in the Christian literature of the first centuries AD, until the invention of the Q theory, any mention of any document reasonably resembling the hypothetical document Q postulated by this hypothesis. By contrast, there is a variety of references by different authors of these times to a Hebrew version of Matthew's Gospel, several parts of which were quoted or translated by several authors.
- There is a considerable number of minor agreements between Matthew's Greek Gospel and Luke against Mark. This number is too large to result from mere chance.

In view of this evidence, the following view seems far more probable: First, Matthew the Apostle wrote his Gospel in Hebrew or Aramaic. Then Mark translated to Greek and published a part of this Gospel, which resulted in what we know today as Mark's Gospel. Luke later also translated Matthew's Gospel into Greek, with the difference that he used a far more complete version of this Gospel, probably also Mark's Gospel itself, and he added some content from his own sources. Independently, an anonymous author, most probably Jewish-Christian, translated Matthew's Gospel into Greek.

This view still has a problem: it does not explain why Mark omitted a large part of Matthew's Gospel. However, unlike the big problems of the Q theory, this one admits a variety of reasonable explanations: the missing part may have been lost accidentally, or perhaps omitted voluntarily. In this respect, it is interesting to observe that, if Mark's community already used a document similar to the Didache, as a catechism or community rule, the parts of Matthew's Gospel that Mark omitted would have been largely redundant with this document; instead, Mark and his community seem to have been far more interested in the facts of Jesus' life than in his teachings, which they probably already knew, and also in his parables and other complementary remarks explaining and clarifying these teachings.

Some critics have suspected that the mainly Protestant Q theory was intended to undermine the prestige of Matthew's Gospel because of its passage in which Jesus designates Peter as Head of the Church and therefore the first Pope [16:18-19], but this hypothetical strategy was probably not intentional. Instead, there may have been an unconscious bias of Protestant scholars against Matthew's Gospel, as explained in the previous section about the nature of beliefs and the dopaminergic system. This confirms that no human is perfect, including the most competent ones.

As for the time of redaction of the original written source of the Synoptics, it is interesting to note that these Gospels contain practically no theology, which is a strong indication that their original author was in direct relation with Jesus, and in any case that this source is much older than any New Testament book containing theology, such as St Paul's Epistles or St John's Gospel.

The Last Supper:

The Synoptic Gospels seem to imply that the Last Supper was a Passover dinner, which apparently contradicts their affirmation that the Friday on which the trial of Jesus took place was the day of the Preparation, at least if we assume that this was the Preparation of the Passover. However, Matthew and Luke mention the 'Preparation' without further precision, whereas Mark, following his custom, complements his source by specifying that it was the Preparation of the Sabbath. With this precision, the Synoptics become coherent within themselves: they imply that this year the Passover fell on Friday, the Last Supper was prepared and took place on Thursday and was the Passover dinner, and the following Friday was both the Passover and the Preparation of the Sabbath. The problems of this version are, on the one hand, that it contradicts John's Gospel [18:28; 19:14,31] and Paul's first Epistle to Corinthians [5:7], and on the other hand that standard astronomical calculations show that during the mandate of Pilate the Passover never fell on Friday, but it fell on Saturday twice, in 30 and 33 AD. To solve these problems, a considerable number of hypotheses have been proposed, for which a detailed review will not be included here, but it can be found for example in [60]. One group of theories hypothesizes the use of different calendars by Jesus and the Jewish authorities, resulting in different dates for the Passover. Another hypothesis postulates that the passage about the preparation of the Passover supper in the Synoptics [Matthew 16:17-19 and parallels] was not originally linked in the text to the continuation about the Last Supper; it merely reported an isolated anecdote, a 'lesser miracle', which could have occurred on another year. The amazing aspect of this anecdote, at least for the disciples, might have been that they wondered how Jesus,

who was always with them, could have arranged deals with strangers unknown to the disciples without them noticing, and in this aspect the anecdote could be compared with that of the donkey used for the Entry into Jerusalem [Matthew 21:2-7 and parallels]. If we eliminate the temporal succession between the anecdote of the preparation of the Passover by the disciples and the subsequent passage about the Last Supper, the Synoptics become compatible with the rest of the New Testament and with standard astronomical calculations. This explanation is not so unlikely as it might seem at first sight: whereas it is obvious that the Synoptics had at least one common written source, it is also obvious that at some level the order of the passages of these sources was not well determined, because there are considerable differences between the Synoptics in the order of the passages that contain no clue about their correct chronological order, and therefore in principle we can suppose that the work of the evangelists included a considerable amount of chronological reconstruction. This problem may have occurred because at some level the common source of the Synoptics was written on unbound pages, which may not have been particularly infrequent in these times, especially for collections of sayings and anecdotes.

Anyway, even without these proposals of harmonization, would this apparent discrepancy of dates really be so important? All sources agree on the fundamental point, that is, that there was a Last Supper a short time before the arrest and trial of Jesus. By contrast, the exact date may be important only for those who believe that the Bible is the direct inspiration of God word by word and therefore cannot be wrong on anything. Certainly, it is reasonable to believe that God has inspired the fundamental precepts contained in the Bible, but does it make sense to believe that he must have inspired also the exact dates of all the events? And in this view, where should we draw the line between the writers, copyists, translators and other scholars who are supposedly covered by the direct inspiration of God and those who are not?

The poor in spirit, the people of good will and the unjust steward:

The passage of Matthew's Gospel where Jesus proclaims "Blessed are the poor in spirit ..." [5:3] and the analogous passage about those "...hungry and thirsty for justice..." [5:6] have seemed suspect to many because the corresponding parallels in Luke's Gospel just refer to the people merely poor and merely hungry. Therefore, it seems important to try to find what were the original words of Jesus. In this respect, we must note that even the oldest available versions of Mathew's Gospel contain the expressions 'in spirit' and 'for justice', so there is no evidence of interpolation. We can also note that the expression 'poor in spirit' can be found in the Qumran manuscripts, and that Matthew's Gospel includes the famous passage where Jesus says that it is easier for a camel to pass through the eye of a needle than for a rich person to enter the Kingdom of Heaven [19, 24]. Therefore, there seems to be no evidence of bad faith, and there can be no doubt that both Gospels coincide in praising humility and strongly criticizing avarice. Even so, it may be interesting to investigate whether we can reproduce the original words of Jesus. In this respect, an invaluable reference is provided by the Gospel of Thomas [§ 54] "Blessed are the poor, because yours is the Kingdom of Heaven". This cannot have been copied from the Gospel of Matthew, which says 'in spirit', nor from Luke's Gospel, which says 'the Kingdom of God', so very probably the original words of Jesus were those reproduced by Thomas' Gospel, which in addition also blesses the merely hungry, with no mention to justice [§ 69].

Two other controversies with some relation with the Qumran literature are the translation "... on earth peace to people of good will" of [Luke 2, 14] and the meaning of the parable of the unjust steward [Luke 16:1-12]. With respect to the first, the oldest versions of this Gospel read literally in Greek "... on earth peace in people of good will" (variant 1), together with the Latin Vulgate of St Jerome and many other versions. By contrast, a very old correction suppressed one letter of the original Greek words, resulting in the meaning "... on earth peace, in people good will" (variant 2). These two different versions remained for centuries in different versions of the Gospel, until, again in the 19th century and following a proposal of Protestant scholars, it was suggested that, although the original Greek words read really "... on earth peace in people of good will", they should be understood as "... on earth peace to people of *God's* good will" (variant 3). Nowadays, the acceptance of this variant is widespread, especially in the Protestant world, and, despite its appearance, it is not completely arbitrary, because it has been justified by the presence in the Qumran Hymns (1QH) of a somewhat comparable expression: "the sons of His benevolence", being understood "of God's benevolence". Furthermore, according to today's knowledge, the variant 1 was not particularly idiomatic at this time either in Hebrew or in Greek. However, the interpretation of variant 3 is objectively problematic at least for the following reasons:

- There is absolutely no reason to suppose that Luke intended to mean ‘of His good will’ while writing “of good will”, when even the Qumran people felt the need to include explicitly the word ‘His’.
- In the parable of the unjust steward, Luke includes an expression very similar to variant 1, “the steward of the injustice” [16:8], which cannot conceivably be interpreted as referring to God’s injustice, which would be a horrible blasphemy. Other examples can be found in [16:9] “money of the injustice”, [18:6] “the judge of the injustice”.
- There is no reason why Luke should have adopted uncritically a piece of Qumranic doctrine, and if fact there seem to have been reasons for the opposite: in the parable of the unjust steward, the so-called ‘children of this world’ are opposed to the ‘children of light’. There can be no doubt that the expression ‘children of light’, which appears profusely in the Qumran literature, refers to the members of the Qumran community, whereas the expression ‘children of this time’ can be found nowhere in the Qumran literature, at least as far as the author knows.

In sum, the interpretation of variant 3 appears objectively unjustifiable for several independent reasons. However, it is interesting to observe that, again, it is the one that best agrees with the Protestant doctrine, and therefore, again, one can suspect an unconscious cognitive bias affecting mainly the Protestant scholars. As for the variants 1 and 2, the first is the one that best reflects the original text while being compatible with Christian doctrine, whereas the second is more divine and Christian in the sense that it reflects the idea that God wants everybody to be saved. Unfortunately, this variant does not correspond to the original wording, and it does not make much sense either. If it had said “on earth peace, good will among people”, as some translations do, there would have been no problem: it would have meant ‘on earth, peace and good will for humans’. However, the exact words are “on earth peace, in people good will”: so for whom is the peace on earth, apart from for humans? For animals? For earth itself? This makes little sense.

Another oddity of the reference passage is that it reads literally ‘... in people of good will’, with the preposition ‘in’, as in ‘Glory to God in the highest ...’. Because of this oddity, the phrase is often translated ‘... towards people...’ or ‘... among people...’, whereas in other passages the equivalent expression is, as expected ‘Peace to you’ [John 20, 21]. However, the preposition ‘in’ has been conserved in the Latin Vulgate since its first available versions, and probably with good reason, because the usage of ‘in’ is perfectly appropriate if the expression refers to interior peace instead of the absence of physical violence. Furthermore, this interpretation is fully compatible with the idea that God wants everybody to be saved. Unfortunately, this interpretation can seem a little disappointing in the sense that it does not seem to condemn physical violence, but in fact it does so indirectly by proclaiming that there will be no peace of mind for people with bad intentions, or even for indifferent ones.

Another interesting question is the ultimate origin of Luke’s passage about the shepherds. As we saw above, Luke might have copied some passages from the Protoevangelium Jacobi, but in this document there seems to be no shepherds... except in the surreal scene of [18:2], where there are no angels and even animals are silent. Could Luke have derived his scene with shepherds and angels from this passage? Surprisingly, this looks possible: The Protoevangelium text describes people and animals immobile and staring at the sky, which at these times was almost routinely considered a sign of some heavenly apparition (for example, Habacuc 2:20, Sophonias 1:7). Therefore, with the logic of his time, Luke might have deduced that the shepherds were witnessing some apparition of angels whose words he reconstructed probably with the help of some respectable oral or written source of his own.

Finally, there remains the question of the interpretation of the parable of the unjust steward, which has puzzled the readers of all times because it seems to praise immoral behavior. In this respect, there have been many proposals, none of which can be considered evident. Perhaps the most probable is that the oddity results from some transmission or translation error or omission. There are indications that Jesus’ parables sometimes were not well understood [Matthew 13:13-17; 34-35; Mark 4:33-34], and people who do not understand well what they are talking about are in general much more prone to errors than those who understand. Some authors have suggested that the steward renounces to his own commissions, but in this case he would have been ‘unjust’ only before the time of the parable, and the money he renounces to could hardly have been considered unjust, unless the rich man himself had earned his fortune by obscure means, such as unlawful usury, in which case there would hardly anything immoral in returning at least part of the unjust money. However, in these cases one would have expected further explanations in the parable, which could indicate some involuntary omission by Luke or his sources. A related subject is that of the uses forbidden by the religious law of these times for money of unlawful origin [Matthew 27:6], which Jesus might have proposed to

supersede, as in [Matthew 12:1-8]. Finally, the interpretation at the limit of Christian morality: on the basis of the preface of the Gospel, where Luke dedicates it to a 'most excellent Theophilus', and the clear penchant of Luke in favor of the poor 'in money', some have hypothesized that he was somehow transmitting and justifying to Theophilus, who was probably an authority with some relation to the Qumranic ideology but also at least some sympathy for Christian beliefs, the idea of acting more or less like a Robin Hood of this time, an administrative, nonviolent Robin Hood. This interpretation does not exclude the possibility that the ultimate source of this parable could have been Jesus himself, the problem being in this case that we do not have enough information to determine whether his words were later modified by mistake or exaggerated.

St Paul and the Protestant doctrine

The Protestant doctrine is essentially based on the principles 'Sola fides, sola scriptura'. The latter has been extensively put into practice by devote Protestants, as shown in the above examples and in the plethora of works that they have published on this subject and are currently available to everybody; by contrast, the Catholic authorities, at least until the 20th century, seem to have been rather secretive about the biblical manuscripts in their possession, even though these manuscripts, which include the prestigious Codex Vaticanus, have finally proved to be of the highest quality among the plethora of biblical manuscripts available today. As for the first principle, "faith only", it is largely based on the doctrine of St Paul [Romans 1 – 15], and in particular on the arch-famous phrase "Abraham believed God, and it was reckoned to him as righteousness". Of course, as usual, one must read the complete doctrine before drawing conclusions. The context is a theological justification by Paul for the validity of the extension of the former Jewish Covenant to Gentiles (= non-Jews) through the sacrifice of God's Son Jesus. Essentially, Paul tries to show that the Gentiles do not have to apply the full law of Moses as long as they believe in Jesus. It was obviously not possible for Abraham to be saved on the basis of his respect for a law that did not exist at his time. As for the Gentiles, it was necessary to justify why they could be exempted from some parts of Moses' law while having to comply with the rest, namely those explicitly endorsed by Jesus. Unfortunately, this theological elaboration has often been considered disquieting by many, who have interpreted that, according to this doctrine, only some people predestined by the arbitrary favor of God can save themselves, and that they can do so essentially regardless of whatever sins they commit. However, Paul explicitly denies that [Romans 6:15] and points out also explicitly that faith in Jesus implies faith in his teachings, enumerated by Paul in the same Epistle, for example: "love one another with brotherly affection... [12:10], "If possible, so far as it depends on you, leave in peace with all humans" [12;18], "... never avenge yourselves, but leave it to the wrath of God..." [12;19], "... thou shall not kill, etc..." [13;9]. According to the teaching of Jesus, all true branches of Christianity admit that nobody can be saved without some help from God, but people must at least do what they can within their possibilities, and a restrictive, let alone selfish or arrogant, view of predestination would be incompatible with Jesus' exigence of humility: the speck and the log in the eye, the places at a marriage feast, the Pharisee and the tax collector, etc.

This example can illustrate why complex theological elaborations can be too easily misunderstood or misinterpreted even by competent scholars, hence the enormous advantage of concise formulas like the Ten Commandments or the Golden Rule. In this respect, Jesus' sayings and parables are strikingly concise and expressive, possible to understand practically by anybody, with just a few possible but dubious exceptions like the parable of the unjust steward, which seems as obscure as its real origin.

Conclusion:

The above examples, which can be easily completed by readers with enough time and resources, show that the knowledge that we have today in relation to the reliability of religious Scriptures is largely sufficient for all really significant points, and that the innumerable variant doctrines or heresies that have appeared since they were written never result from impartial good faith interpretations, but rather from questionable interpretations, more or less intentional, of the original text, or extractions of quotes out of their original context. Furthermore, in the case of the New Testament, it appears that the (considerable) work of reconstructing the life and original words of Jesus had already been done very meticulously by the Church Fathers of the 1st – 4th centuries AD, and its results have not been substantially improved by the massive intellectual work of the 19th – 21st centuries, even with the help of today's technologies.

To illustrate the reliability of the reports given by the New Testament about subjects of different importance, one can consider the following examples:

- It is reported in the Gospel of Matthew and the Protoevangelium Jacobi that shortly after his birth Jesus was visited by some Magi, who brought him three presents, but hardly anything more is specified about these people. Some centuries later, different contradictory traditions had already specified how many of them there were, whether they were kings or not, where they came from, and their supposed names [61]. The only reasonable basis for any of these traditions was that, since there were three presents, gold, incense and myrrh, one could suppose in principle that there were three Magi.
- By contrast, it was always unanimously admitted that there were 12 apostles, although with some secondary ambiguities not affecting the main protagonists: Matthew / Levi, Bartholomew / Nathanael, James the son of Alphaeus / James the Less / James the brother of Jesus.
- As for the real protagonists, Jesus of course, and at least Mary, Peter, or James and John sons of Zebedee, the agreement between the different sources is maximal.

5.3.3 Religion and morality

One of the most fundamental arguments that have always been adduced in favor of religions, and also the chief motive of suspicion of believers with respect to atheists, is that **religions have a moral teaching**. And consequently, one of the main arguments that atheists have tried to adduce against religions is that, according to a variety of sources whose supposed validity will be evaluated below, religions traditionally have not made people good, but they have in general made them worse than the absence of religion.

To begin with, these atheistic claims are manifestly absurd at least when attacking Christianity: if a religion unmistakably commands to love our enemies, offer the other cheek, and treat everybody as we would want to be treated, how is it possible to use this religion in good faith to justify the atrocities that aggressive atheists claim to have been committed in the name of religion? No matter how you look at this question, it is **patently self-evident**, by definition and by the pure nature and logic of things, that such atrocities have been committed **despite** the Christian teachings instead of because of them. Any other idea is at best surrealistic: if something is true, it cannot be false; if something is red, it cannot be blue; and if some doctrine forbids violence, then it cannot induce violence. That some criminals have used Christian teachings in bad faith as a pretext for their crimes, as they could have used any other pretext, religious or not, does not justify in any way the absurd claim of atheists that it was the religion that caused these crimes.

As for atheism, it is true, as our reference atheists claim, that it does not induce violence by itself, but it does not forbid it either. Therefore, it is unquestionable that, from the point of view of violence, atheism is considerably worse than religions like Christianity or Buddhism, which explicitly forbid violence. In other words, when atheists claim that the notorious historic criminals who were atheists did not commit their crimes induced by atheism itself, they may be right, but they 'forget' to point out that these crimes would have probably been avoided or at least reduced if these criminals had been subject to the influence of nonviolent religions.

Since atheism in itself is an essentially negative idea compatible with practically any kind of action or rule, good or bad, it is useless and potentially dangerous unless completed by some constructive idea. It is too easy and sometimes dangerous to criticize the ideas of others without proposing something better as a replacement. In this respect, the recurrent concept mentioned by most atheists for this replacement is **humanism**, for which in principle the following considerations apply:

- There is no unique definition of humanism universally accepted, and our reference atheists do not provide it. However, if the moral teaching of the adopted variant of humanism is based on the universal form of the Golden Rule "Treat others as you would want to be treated", then in principle everything is fine.
- Practically all definitions of humanism exclude any form of religious belief. This is fine as long as it is clearly affirmed that religious believers are as worthy of respect and justice as any other human as long as they also respect the universal Golden Rule, that atheism is just an option, and that it is strictly impossible to prove beyond doubt either that God exists or that he does not exist. Otherwise, there would be the risk of presenting good faith religious believers as 'others' in an emotional context of in-group morality, that

is, of presenting religious believers respecting universal GR as somehow 'bad', which must be avoided at all costs.

- Another common aspect of practically all definitions of humanism is the absolute predominance of reason and experience over irrational forms of knowledge. There are some problems with this view:
 - As shown in sections 2 and 5.3.1, reason by itself does not suffice to provide an adequate knowledge of the world in which we live. Unfortunately, reason is as prone to error as any other human way to acquire knowledge, and this is especially true for children, who still do not have the basic knowledge, experience and abilities necessary for proper reasoning.
 - This view does not specify what forms of experience are valid: personal experience, which is necessarily very limited, or scientific experiments, of which the overwhelming majority must be performed and interpreted by others, or personal experience reported by other common people. The last two categories imply a serious problem of trust that can overwhelm practically any common person but most especially children.
 - Zealous humanists have already had the questionable idea of trying to educate children in a context of 'humanism', which implies the risk of overwhelming them with evaluations of reliability and trustworthiness that are complicated even for adults, and multiplies the risk of misinterpretation of the preceding points. More details on this subject are given later in this section.

As for the religions that promote or tolerate violence under certain circumstances, or did so in the past, it would be diabolically difficult for any human scholar, let alone for our reference atheists, to determine reliably whether ultimately these religions have predominantly generated violence or, on the contrary, have moderated a violence that would have been worse otherwise. For this superhuman task, it would be necessary to know each and every verse of the Scriptures of these religions, plus the complete detailed information available about the history of these religions, including all alternative religions and atheistic ideologies, and master the original languages of all these documents, with the additional problem that the believers of these religions initiated their history of violence before their Scriptures were put in written form; and all that for a study whose results could be understood only by people with similar competences. It would certainly be much easier to evaluate hypothetical religions promoting or allowing violence without restriction, but fortunately such religions are not significant nowadays, if they exist at all, and anyway our atheists have failed in the equally easy task of evaluating the religions that condemn violence under any circumstance. Furthermore, the really important question is whether all significant religions are compatible nowadays with the universal Golden Rule and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of the United Nations, and this is a question that our reference atheists fail to address properly, although respected representatives of all of today's significant religions claim that there is actually such compatibility, as reflected in the Declaration for a Global Ethic elaborated with the participation of relevant religious and spiritual leaders [49, 50].

As illustration and complement for these general remarks, we analyze below in further detail some of the claims of our two representative atheists, to show more explicitly the real value of their arguments.

To begin with, one must take into account that, practically until the 19th century, religion was in practice totally integrated with politics, law and what we call today science; all that was essentially the same thing. Therefore, it is now too easy, but invariably false, to claim that before this time political decisions, including wars, or excesses in law enforcement, were the responsibility of religion, because there was no other guide available. Instead, believers could claim that, in fact, religions moderated the innate sinister instincts of the political rulers of these times. Furthermore, even in the 20th century, Mr. Dawkins admits for example that, despite the names of the fighting factions, the Northern Ireland conflict is of political nature [GD ch 7.3, p 294]. It is also rather unfair and tendentious, as too many atheists do, to criticize and even ridicule outdated beliefs of ancient times, because the reason of their invalidity was essentially the deficiency of the technology of their time. That, for example, some diseases were attributed to demons or 'humors' just reflects the medical knowledge of these times, for which religions could provide no better alternative than those given by the current medical knowledge. Even so, some religious laws seem to have anticipated modern medicine by thousands of years: for example the laws about diet or leprosy of the Hebrew bible anticipated immunology and microbiology, and, according to the available sources, Jesus can be reasonably supposed to have performed a good number of curations considered miraculous at his time, though possibly exaggerated by later oral transmission.

That religious precepts have been fundamental for millennia for the survival of human societies does not imply that they cannot be changed as technology advances, but only, of course, if they depend on technology, with the most extreme precautions, and on the basis of hard, incontrovertible evidence uncovered by advanced technology and understandable by any common citizen. For example, the traditional strict laws about marriage and adultery became largely obsolete when it became possible to determine without doubt who is the biological father of anybody. As for the precepts about leprosy and other diseases, modern hygiene and the discovery of antibiotics and other antimicrobial and antiparasitic agents have also made these precepts obsolete, at least in part, because unrestricted contagion is still not advisable. Other precepts such as the weekly rest and the teachings of Jesus about good will, gentleness, solidarity and peace of mind still do not seem to have been scientifically understood, although they are physiologically invaluable to ensure the necessary repair of the organism and the correct working of the nervous and immune systems. As for the Jewish dietary laws, in our times of industrial food processing it is probably advisable to consider that the physiological benefit of these laws might be, in addition to limiting the risk of being infected by parasites, to allow the organism to learn to anticipate the properties of ingested food by its taste and immunological profile, and for this purpose it is still advisable to limit one's diet to a restricted variety of known foods and avoid preparing fine mixtures of them, so that the organism can easily identify those that we ingest. In addition, we should limit our diet to foods in their natural form, to prevent our digestive system from degenerating because of the lack of work resulting from eating too easily digestible food. This restriction does not affect traditional cooking, for which humans have had more than a million years to adapt their digestive system, but it should apply to modern industrially processed food, which has already been proved harmful for our health. Other foods that should be avoided are those containing psychoactive substances, whether naturally occurring or added artificially, like the so-called flavor enhancers, because they may disorient the brain about the real value of the food. If one really cannot go without psychoactive substances, at last one can try to avoid them during meals and to avoid mixing them with food.

There is also the problem of determining what we should adopt as moral criteria if we renounce to the guide of religious precepts. Mr. Dawkins [GD ch 7.4, p 298-299] proposes some 'New Ten Commandments', which are essentially the Golden Rule, some recommendations also given by religious and secular wisdom, and also some questionable precepts, such as "always check your ideas against the facts" and "Question everything", which are not realistic because very few people, if any, can afford to do that in most circumstances. Furthermore, the latter precept introduces us again in the realm of circular surrealism, because there is no reason to avoid applying it to all these commandments, including the precept "Question everything" itself, unless it is meant to be understood as "Question everything except what I say", which does not even deserve further comment.

In any human society, it is impossible to live without massively trusting others, because it is impossible to verify by oneself all the facts that might be relevant to us. This is true regardless of the technological level, because, as technology advances, whereas the accessibility of information increases, its volume and complexity also grow, making advanced knowledge increasingly difficult to understand for non-specialists. By contrast, it is usually easier to evaluate the reliability of people than that of scientific theories. Therefore, instead of the naïve precepts quoted by Mr. Dawkins, one misses some well-known common-sense recommendations, such as:

Beware of people ...

- ... who don't respect the Golden Rule.
- ... who don't practice what they preach.
- ... who contradict themselves.
- ... who are caught lying, even only once ("... if you deceive me twice, it's my fault").
- ... who change their ideas or opinions, except exceptionally and for solid and transparent reasons.
- ... who don't keep their promise, except in case of unexpected force majeure.
- ... who look excited, vehement, arrogant, vain or histrionic.
- ... who defend or justify themselves without being questioned ("Excusatio non petita...").
- ... who are nice with you but not with others, especially if you are rich or attractive ("First they came for...").
- ... who make their living from obscure, immoral or illegal sources, or from propagating controversial ideas.
- ... who offend or corrupt people, or sow discord.
- ... who are part of the answer to the question "Cui prodest?" in unclear situations.

As for Mr. Harris, he proposes a deeply disquieting supposedly scientific approach to morality, which will be commented on later.

We review below in more detail some quotations about religion and morality from our reference atheists.

[GD ch 6.2] about a possible Darwinian origin of our moral sense. It is true that some concepts related to morality, such as the sense of justice, and of course those of loving, hating, benefiting or harming others, are innate in humans, as well as in other superior animals. However, the possible practical use of this idea to determine what we should do in practice would be very dangerous, because this could imply the following fatal errors:

- Naïve people might deduce from this idea that morality amounts essentially to do what we feel eager or compelled to do, or what we instinctively feel to be correct, which can be a big mistake if only because this is precisely what drug addicts do. One must realize that, although the concepts of justice and reciprocity are innate, the distinction between the ‘fellows’ or ‘neighbors’ to which the instinctive Golden Rule must be applied, and the ‘enemies’ or ‘others’ who supposedly do not deserve this treatment, is not innate, but must be learned, and the purely instinctive difference of treatment towards ‘fellows’ and ‘others’ can be abysmal and often criminal. Of course, interactions with others more complicated than just killing or hitting them must also be learned. For example, some authors have remarked that, for most humans, it is instinctively less repulsive and gruesome to press a button that triggers the detonation of nuclear devices killing millions of people than killing just one person with one’s own hands. In sum, what the genes give us is the ability to use the concepts related to morality, but applying these concepts correctly depends on us, on our free will.
- Less naïve people might deduce, or pretend to deduce, that the rules of morality must be ‘calculated’ so as to maximize the adaptation of the group / tribe / society to its environment. This idea is extremely dangerous because:
 - As shown in section 2.5, the evolution of live beings has not resulted only from natural selection.
 - Even if it had, it would remain to be proved that the rules applicable to animals are valid for humans.
 - In practice, throughout human history moral behavior has not been determined by innate instincts or Darwinian calculation, but by the teachings revealed by God or the ‘gods’ of each human group.
 - In any case, this kind of calculation is far too complicated for the human mind, as shown in sec. 2.
 - Worst of all, the idea of Darwinian evolution of humans is sinisterly prone to justify the worst and most massive crimes, as proved by its use by nazis, racists, eugenics activists, or just plain criminals driven by avarice or megalomania.

In consequence, the practical application of the mere idea of Darwinian morality, even in good faith, which, though not very frequent, may happen, must be radically rejected in favor of traditional morality. Trying to reason about morality should be considered not only a mistake, but an extremely dangerous and irresponsible insanity: even the least error, let alone tendentiousness, can result in hideous crimes. The reader can find a more extensive criticism of Darwinian morality in [62]; the whole book is worth reading, but the part about Darwinian morality is particularly interesting.

[GD ch 6.3, p 262] Mr. Dawkins includes a quotation from Mr. Harris reporting that in the US the states voting predominantly for Republicans have in general higher criminality rates than those voting for Democrats. Since in principle Republicans are usually considered to be in a large part conservative Christians, this would mean that Christian religiosity correlates positively with higher criminality rates. As usual, even though he includes the quotation, Mr. Dawkins admits that “Correlational evidence is never conclusive”, and he is right, because that A correlates with B does not necessarily mean that A causes B, because it may be B that causes A, or both may result from a third cause C. In this case, for example, without further information we can also interpret that the citizens of the states with higher levels of criminality vote for Republican politicians because they perceive them to be tougher on crime and more generally on immorality. Much the same might be occurring nowadays with extreme-right parties in Europe, America and some other locations, because these parties are increasingly perceived to be potentially tougher on criminality and immorality than their traditional moderate counterparts.

On the other hand, it seems certain that, in general, religiosity is negatively correlated with economic wealth, that is, that the rich are generally less religious than the poor, but there is a simple explanation for that: in general, in affluent societies, people find no particular difficulties to solve their practical problems with the secular rules of their societies,

so they do not feel the need to search for answers elsewhere; by contrast, when these rules do not provide acceptable solutions, many people switch to beliefs of another nature, either in traditional religions or new systems of belief. In consequence, a possible correlation of religiosity with criminality could in fact result from the higher criminality rate of poor societies, not from any property of religions inducing crime, as tendentious atheists claim.

[GD ch 7.2, p 287] "... the moral considerations for others ... apparently promoted by the Old and New Testaments was originally intended to apply only to a narrowly defined in-group". This is false for the New Testament: in addition to the precept "Love your neighbor as yourself", the New Testament has always contained the universal positive form of the Golden Rule "Whatever you wish that humans (*anthropoi* in the original Greek version) do to you, do so to them" [Matthew 7:12, Luke 6:31]. It is true that the Golden Rule is not, in principle, about love, but about justice, but it requires everybody who likes to be treated with love to treat others with love also. In addition, the Didache also reproduces this precept, although with a subtlety: for 'non-neighbors', it suffices to apply the negative form of the GR "do not treat others as you would not want to be treated". In any case, none of these precepts can be considered in-group morality. Furthermore, nowadays practically all religions accept the universal form of the Golden Rule [49, 50].

[GD ch 8.6, p 347] Mr. Dawkins, in his unlimited antireligious zeal, proposes to avoid teaching children that faith is a virtue. However, he misses the point, again. Children, and even also adults, innately tend to learn by emulation, that is, they tend to imitate the people whom they trust and admire. If they do not find in their real environment models suitable for this purpose, that is, people who are perceived as righteous, benevolent, and powerful or prestigious, perhaps morally, they will look for models elsewhere, in available indirect reports of whatever kind. Therefore, the problem is not faith, but the behavior of the models. The problem occurs when the personages adopted as models harm people, and most especially people who do not deserve it. Furthermore, children must be dissuaded from trying to punish anybody themselves, they must be encouraged, in case of problems, to ask for help from trusted adults, that is, their parents, tutors, or, in their absence, trusted relatives or official authorities. Additionally, of course, the people with these responsibilities should also prevent children from being exposed to models behaving dangerously or imprudently. However, these rules only work if parents or tutors genuinely love their children, and other relatives and authorities at least care for them; otherwise, children might be tempted to look for help elsewhere, with potentially catastrophic, life-ruining consequences. As children grow up and become adolescents, it progressively becomes less dangerous that they form their own criteria, while still abstaining from trying to punish anybody themselves, which is reserved to authorities, and it becomes normal that they ask their parents for justifications for their instructions, but even so the demands for explanations of little children must be answered with love and tact; all children can understand the concepts of helping or harming others, and most can understand the concept of justice and the Golden Rule instinctively; however, in relation to moral behavior, sometimes there may be no better answer than 'God ordered it, and you will go to hell if you do not obey, and please note that God sees everything'. Alternatively, some educators may have the idea of invoking creatures like ogres or witches, but in this case it should be made clear that God is infinitely just, and therefore ogres, witches, dishonest politicians and other evil creatures can harm people only in the case and to the degree that God permits them because of the bad behavior of the victims. The unfortunate precept of Mr. Dawkins refers to children without any indication of age, and perhaps only to religious faith, but anyway what must be avoided at all costs is to encourage children and adolescents to object systematically to everything just for the sake of objection or contradiction, and influencing them specifically against religions proclaiming the universal GR would be precisely the same kind of brainwashing that Mr. Dawkins reproaches to believers. Perhaps Mr. Dawkins expects five-year-old children to read his books, and even understand them, which is difficult even for adults? Or perhaps he fears that the children who believe in God will inescapably conserve this belief throughout their whole lives? Is this what happens with, say, Santa Claus or Cinderella? There have been plenty of people who were religious even in their early adulthood and then became atheists, and inversely many adult atheists later became believers.

On the other hand, since we have mentioned the innate tendency to admiration and emulation of children and adolescents, but also adults, it may be interesting to discuss this tendency in further detail and also to propose a theory about the nature and causes of an essentially inverse emotion: laughter, and more generally the sense of humor, which has puzzled humans of all times and has been the subject of innumerable speculations. These types of emotion are discussed below in sections 5.5 and 5.6.

[ML ch 1, p 57] Mr. Harris informs us that the God of Abraham taught us to kill our children for "talking back to us" and quotes in this respect the Gospels of Mark and Luke in addition to the Old Testament. However, there are several

inaccuracies in his passage. The New Testament passages are in fact quotations of the Old Testament taken out of context, and in turn the Old Testament does not refer to people who merely talk back to their parents, but who curse them, which may be essentially the same nowadays, but not in their time. Furthermore, the Old Testament does not instruct us to kill our children in these cases, but says generically that the culprit “will die”. We can also remark that, in these times, life was far tougher than today, and therefore, unfortunately, human life was less valuable than today, and people were therefore less impressed by benign punishments; in addition, in these societies parental authority was more important than in today’s Western societies.

Other unacceptable omissions of Mr. Harris on this subject are the passages of the Gospels that show the real opinion of Jesus about children and these old laws: “Let the children come to me...” [Matthew 19:13-15 and parallels], “Whoever receives one such child in my name receives me”, “Whoever causes one of these little ones who believe in me to sin... better be drowned in the depth of the sea” [Matthew 18:5-7 and parallels], and the parable of the lost son [Luke 15:11-32]. Furthermore, with respect to adultery, which was another misdeed that the Hebrew Bible mentioned as worth the death penalty, we have the famous passage of the adulterous woman [John 8:1-11]: “Let him who is without sin among you be the first to throw a stone at her”.

Finally, the most scaring aspect of Mr. Harris’ 2010 book, reflected in its subtitle “How science can determine human values”, and the whole chapter 5. The mere idea that people should feel happy or honest according to what some machine says gives the creeps, even if this idea is not reflected for now in any form of compulsory rule. In sum, the arguments of Mr. Harris seem to be as follows: first, actions supposedly cannot have **moral value** by themselves, because there is no universal agreement on this subject; however, Mr. Harris ignores the practically universal agreement of today’s religions on a global ethic based on the Golden Rule [49, 50]. In fact, Mr. Harris practically ignores the Golden Rule: it is not referenced in the index of his book, and it is mentioned only en passant, and with yet another accumulation of false claims or half-truths [ML ch 2, p 105, quotes in *italic*, stress ours]: (1) ‘*religions differ considerably in their doctrines*’: perhaps, but not in their moral doctrine nowadays [49, 50]; (2) ‘*many religions ... like Christianity ... countenance slavery*’; (3) ‘... *the Golden Rule ... is something we bring to scripture, it does not come from scripture*’: this is completely false: the universal Golden Rule, which is of course incompatible with slavery, was already proclaimed at least by Christianity 2000 years ago, and by Buddhism and Confucianism five centuries before that; (4) ‘*the reasons to believe that any of the world’s religions were revealed ... are either risible or nonexistent*’: this is just Mr. Harris’ opinion, unjustified and offensive. Therefore, after excluding moral values as possible references, Mr. Harris adopts as a ‘starting point’ **consequentialism** (the idea that actions are moral only on the basis of their consequences) and implicitly evaluates **utilitarianism** (the idea that morality should maximize collective well-being). Then he ‘discovers’ problems that were already well-known: it is practically impossible to calculate, or even only define, the ‘sum’ of the ‘happineses’ of a group of people, let alone of all the individuals of a society. He then ‘deduces’ that we are all wrong about moral values and only ‘science’ can help us. This is wrong, again: certainly, it is very difficult in practice to try to maximize the global well-being of a human group or society, and most often only a compromise is possible, but this does not mean in any way that people are unable to determine by themselves what makes them happy. Fortunately, Mr. Harris does not specify what he has in mind as a possible scientific theory of collective morality or a tool intended for this purpose; however, we can note that this tool already exists: it is called **vote**, and the political systems in which it takes place are called **democracies**. Certainly, nowadays these systems are not perfect: they require a collective culture of honesty and democracy, access to information and freedom of expression; they are vulnerable to violence, dishonesty and slander, and they can still be improved, for example by voting more frequently or voting separately about different subjects. Democracy also requires a high-level law (constitution, UDHR) and its associated judicial subsystem or authority, or more generally a suitable equalitarian mechanism, to prevent any inhuman treatment of minorities. However, instead, Mr. Harris seems to claim essentially that we are all (except perhaps him and some of the ‘experts’ he quotes) stupid automata who do not even know what makes us happy and therefore need the moral supervision of Mr. Harris’ theories and technology. His entire explanation gives the disquieting and somewhat offensive impression of being based on an unacceptably (though perhaps naively) simplistic model of human behavior based essentially on immediate self-interest, comparable to the notorious ‘homo economicus’ at the origin of most unrealistic economic theories. Certainly, democracies are not perfect and even the wisest people of all times have not been perfect either, but it remains to be proved (not ‘scientifically’ of course, because humans are involved, but in a way understandable by everybody and without involving real people in dubious experiments) that Mr. Harris’ ‘scientific’ theories are or will be better than democracy and human wisdom in real situations. So far, all artificial computational approaches to the human mind, let alone to human societies, have completely failed, in

agreement with the section 2 of this document. The use of computers, even those considered AI, will never be a solution, because these machines can only reflect, directly or indirectly, the moral principles of their human designers, plus an unpredictable but likely considerable quantity of errors of design and programming. As for chemical or surgical roads to 'happiness', the application of 'science' has so far been disastrous, as recalled in section 5.3.1. Disquietingly, or even frighteningly, it would seem that what Mr. Harris implies, although he does not say it explicitly, is that, because of all these 'imperfections', when he and his accomplices finally complete their 'scientific' theory of morality we will all be better off *if a computer votes for us*, which is a monstrosity even if supposedly well-intentioned (the road to hell is paved with good intentions... but most often with bad ones). Please let science and technology do only what they really do well to improve human happiness, like providing enough acceptable food and water, housing and hygienic conditions, and real cures for physical diseases, at least when possible, when these diseases are not irremediably caused by the addictions of their victims, while of course abstaining from promoting these addictions in any way.

5.4 Theories in favor of religions

Many authors have adduced arguments in favor of religion on the basis of the currently prevailing scientific views of the universe. Scientists who wrote books in favor of religion include Francis Collins, John Polkinghorne and Arthur Peacocke, and many other scientists are or were also religious believers [63], while for many others, such as S. J. Gould, Peter Higgs or Martin Rees, together with many atheistic non-scientists [58], science and religion are compatible and can coexist peacefully. More recently, a new book has been published on this subject, reportedly with the advice of numerous competent scientists [64]. Logically, we will not review in this section the arguments of these publications that are already treated elsewhere in this document. However, we must observe at least that the common argument consisting in using the Big Bang theory to prove that the universe was created is invalidated by the fact that this theory is wrong, as shown in the section 2.5.1 of this document and also in the references provided in section 3.2. Therefore, in principle this scientific argument in favor of religion should be reformulated as follows: if the Big Bang theory were correct, this would imply that the universe was created, and if it were not correct, this would imply that modern science is not better than any religion on the subject of cosmology.

5.5 Devotion, veneration: the marvelous, transcendent or sacred

Children, and even also adults, innately tend to learn by emulation, that is, they tend to imitate the people whom they trust and admire. This impulse results from the emotion that induces us to perceive people or things, depending on the cases and often by extension, as authoritative, charismatic, prestigious, transcendent, marvelous, or sacred, and in less solemn domains reflects concepts or attributes such as fashion(able), 'in', 'fans', 'it rocks', etc. For lack of a better word, as a compromise between all the possible forms and degrees of this emotion, we can call it **devotion** or **veneration**, or, perhaps more appropriately or descriptively, **the sense of the marvelous**. When informal, this emotion is often associated with the concept of play, and its main negative counterpart is boredom, which occurs in the absence of environmental stimuli with the properties enumerated above. The positive form of this emotion is in general inhibited by fear, hunger, or nervous or physiological stress, and this inhibition must be spared at all costs to children and adolescents because for them emulation and play are an integral part of their psychophysical development.

That this emotion often occurs in religious contexts, which is undeniable, especially in mystic variants, apparently has led aggressive atheists to identify this emotion with religious belief itself and therefore to claim that this kind of belief is irrational, all of which is completely wrong because, on the one hand, religious belief can be based fundamentally on reason and experience, and unfortunately sometimes also on fear, as shown in previous sections, and on the other hand because the perception of the marvelous can be felt, always irrationally, with respect to practically anybody or anything outside any religious context, such as scientific theories or authorities to begin with, but also political or philosophical ideas or authorities, including in particular scientific fundamentalism and atheism, or in the domains of art, technology, clothing, hobbies..., and of course fairy tales and their protagonists, superheroes, works of fiction in general, etc. The variety of uses of the words 'idol' and 'idolize', or 'veneration' and 'venerate', in the religious and secular domains, is a good illustration of this polyvalence.

5.6 The sense of humor

Considering the two fundamental aspects of the sense of humor, that is, that it always implies some superiority felt in relation to the protagonists of the comical situation, and that it induces, in normal circumstances, a mixture of benevolence and satisfaction, and following without much enthusiasm Mr. Dawkins' tendency to look for adaptive evolution nearly everywhere, we will propose the idea that this feeling has been 'intended' by nature primarily as a

reaction of parents, or more generally adults, but also children or adolescents, to the mistakes or mischievous activities of children. Therefore, a healthy sense of humor should always be indulgent and benevolent, whereas in adults sarcasm, mockery, derision and most especially the humiliation of others should be considered pathological and morally despicable, most especially if the victims are children.

It can be noted also that the concepts of fun and boredom are ambiguous or polyvalent, because they can apply in principle either to play or emulation, or to the view or reading of marvelous stories, or to the exercise of the sense of humor, or to all of them, because they are not incompatible if they are directed to different subjects. However, solemn forms of devotion are not fun, and their absence looks more like depression than boredom.

5.7 Reality, fiction, imagination

A well-known feature of the human mind, essential for our high-level intellectual activity, and with a close relationship with the senses of devotion and humor, is the capacity to run thoughts in a mental simulation environment, which, depending on the cases, is usually called **imagination** or **abstract thought**. Unlike the senses of devotion and humor, it is not emotional, but purely computational; however, it can elicit emotions much in the same way as perceptions of reality, although in principle with less intensity. The mental processes of this kind are also very different from dreams or hallucinations, because they are fully coherent and the people who experience them are fully aware that what they are thinking is not real. Therefore, by themselves, the mental processes of this kind are not likely to cause people to perceive or remember as real any fact that only occurs in their imagination. Unfortunately, this does not mean that imagination is free from any possible form of abuse: on the contrary, it is particularly prone to abuse because it allows us to feel a variety of interesting emotions practically without effort or risk. This abuse has happened since the dawn of humankind, and it is particularly frequent nowadays in rich societies, where many people can spend much leisure time without doing anything useful, and works of fiction of all kinds are massively available to the public. An archetype of this abuse is the famous Don Quixote, but unfortunately there are many references of similar cases affecting real people. They occur when people spend too much time immersed in fictional or artificial environments, and the cause of the problem is that the innate tendency to emulation that we all have is massively applied to fictional or artificial 'idols'. The problem can be produced not only by fictional work intended for entertainment, but also by historical accounts, philosophical or supposedly scientific theories, etc. Strictly speaking, the people who have this problem do not lose their sense of reality, but instead develop an unusual, compulsive, almost always inappropriate, and sometimes dangerous or criminal way of dealing with reality, based on the emulation of their fictional idols.

From the point of view of artificial intelligence, a possible computer version of imagination does not seem easy to develop, because there are many possible situations with subtle differences. First, of course, imagination must be distinguished from the perception of reality, but also, within imagination, we may imagine either fictional people in fictional situations, or real people in fictional situations, or fictional people in real situations, or even real people in real situations, for example after having read a report about real facts. On the other hand, when we enjoy a work of fiction, this work and the people who prepared it are real, and the plot also; it is what appears in the plot which is not real, but even so this work may portray real people, as in novels or films based on real facts. In the same way, an enormous amount of the information about real events that we assimilate daily is stored in our brains much in the same form as fictional events, because we did not really witness these real events, which might have occurred thousands of kilometers away, or in dangerous places, etc. Then in these cases, should the people and events that we are representing in our mind be considered real, or fictional? Things are clearly much more subtle. We must also consider that those who reported to us these supposedly real facts may have lied or committed errors, in all or in part, so the only certain fact might be that we received from a certain person or organization a report saying so and so.

Important warning: We must not let the typical innocence of children and fairy tales fool us into believing that imagination and the sense of devotion are innocuous by nature. On the contrary, they may have been the cause of the worst crimes of human history, when children, and perhaps also some adults, were exposed to real or fictional tales of criminal or just violent activities. Therefore, it is of vital importance to avoid exposing children, and preferably also adults if it is not necessary, to episodes of violence, immorality or recklessness, real or fictional. This does not mean that history must be rewritten as a collection of lies, however well-intentioned, but at least that historic immoralities or reckless decisions should not be presented too explicitly, and should preferably be completely omitted for children, and that historical personages responsible for immoral or reckless actions should not be glorified in any way. As for fiction works, immoral episodes and examples of recklessness must be simply avoided, except perhaps in the works of

past times, for which at least the access of children to works containing, let alone praising immoralities or dangerous behavior must be avoided at all costs. The extreme importance of these rules is reflected for example in the severe words of Jesus “Whoever causes one of these little ones to sin, it would be better for him to be thrown into the sea with a millstone hung round his neck” and “Woe to those by whom the temptation comes” [Matthew 18:6-7 and parallels]. Similarly, in our times of massive, almost industrial production of fictional works and ‘virtual’ environments of all kinds, the following extension of the Golden Rule seems to have become mandatory: “Neither do, nor show to others, most especially to children, anything that you would not want for yourself”.

5.8 Popular ‘esoteric’ or ‘paranormal’ beliefs and fiction literature

5.8.1 Telepathy, telekinesis, divination

For this group of beliefs, an interesting compendium is given in the novels of Dan Brown, who knows what interests people and has bothered to do some investigation about the literature related to the subjects he treats. In particular, in his novels ‘Origin’ and ‘The Secret of Secrets’, he treats the subjects of telepathy and extra-sensorial perception, together with the origin of life and Artificial General Intelligence. We include below some comments in relation to these subjects:

- The direct references of the author of this article show consistently that, although telepathy and telekinesis are real, they are far too weak to be of any practical use. Apparently, the human mind has not evolved to transmit mental information or move objects directly, but instead through the use of tools or machines. In consequence, the remote mental perception described in The Secret of Secrets must be considered in principle impossible. The characters of this book who try to use the human mind to spy people thousands of kilometers away had better use their resources to develop machines suitable for this task, in the same way as radio emitters and receptors can transmit information through radio waves practically worldwide without any unnatural mental effort or superpower.
- This book gives some particular views about dreams that may be worth analyzing. On the one hand, the supposed premonitory aspect of a certain dream [65] finally turns out to be the result of an elaborate hoax [66]. On the other hand, the book suggests that the reduction of the ‘censorship’ exerted on conscious thought by the inhibitory neurotransmitter GABA during dreams or under the action of hallucinogens could open the mind to a variety of esoteric information inaccessible to a fully conscious mind [67]. This idea is not new: priests, shamans, sorcerers and even scientists of all times have interpreted dreams, induced naturally or with the help of substances, as possible manifestations of cryptic or supernatural knowledge; for example the Bible, including the New Testament, is full of scenes in which angels or God himself communicate with people through dreams. Dreams and hallucinations are further discussed in section 5.9.
- Outside the paranormal domain, the final arrangement in The Secret of Secrets [68] evokes a critical problem for which so far no complete systematic human solution has ever been found, our best solutions being based on compromises: “Quis custodiet ipsos custodes?”, that is, “Who will guard the guards?”, “Who will monitor the monitors?”. Anyway, even though no perfect solution has been found, the separation of powers, legal controls and freedom of press of modern democratic societies are much better than nothing.
- The author of this article does not have any direct reference of real prophetic abilities, and the indirect references available in modern literature seem in principle compatible with pure chance.
- The mere possibility of existence of a human-made computer like the Winston of ‘Origin’ has been excluded in the above section 2 for any possible degree of human technological progress.
- The hypothesis that the appearance of life might have been merely an effect of the laws of physics, as proposed in ‘Origin’, leads nowhere, as Robert Langdon, and therefore Dan Brown himself, remarks [69]: we can accept that the laws of physics are powerful enough to create life, but who created the laws of physics?

5.8.2 UFOs, little or big green men, Bigfoot and the like, apparitions

These subjects are rather complex but in principle they can be reduced to the common problem of determining whether a given person or group of people who claim to have witnessed some exceptional event ...:

- 1) have really experienced it, that is, the event really occurred.
- 2) have imagined it but they are convinced that it was real for some reason, such as error, misperception or hallucination, etc.
- 3) have invented it intentionally, that is, it was just a lie.

More precisely, most experts agree that there seems to be a profusion of cases 2 and 3 almost in all the above domains, and the fundamental question that remains is whether there has ever been even just one case of type 1, that is, in which one such event really occurred.

Of course, we will not try to analyze here one by one all the cases related to the above subjects, so we will only propose some comments:

- The sightings of UFOs in the form of strange lights seem particularly abundant in situations of presumable lack or insufficiency of sleep.
- The reported abductions by extraterrestrials involve beings that are both too anthropomorphic and too heterogeneous, which strongly suggests that they were not real, although it can always be claimed that these beings appear intentionally as anthropomorphic because their real aspect is too horrible for humans. This is different from the case of God and angels, who must necessarily be imagined as anthropomorphic because the human brain cannot imagine them otherwise.
- Lack of sleep, hallucinations, or similar phenomena cannot explain by themselves collective sightings and can hardly explain recurrent individual sightings.
- The proportion of cases in which the witnesses were children, and were more than one, seems clearly higher for the apparitions of the Virgin Mary than for the other kinds of unnatural events mentioned above. However, it is still difficult to draw conclusions from these facts: children have more imagination than adults and are less likely to fabricate false testimonies, so in principle for them the case 3 seems unlikely; however, for this kind of apparitions, unlike UFOs, Bigfoot or the like, the case 1 would be fulfilled just by some external power inducing in the witnesses the conviction of having seen the supernatural person or phenomenon, without this person being materially present or this phenomenon actually occurring, which would be absurd for UFOs and the like.

In addition, since some possible negative consequences of lack of sleep have been mentioned, the author would like to point out that lack of sleep is much more than that; it is a real curse, whose sinister consequences can extend far beyond merely seeing luminous UFOs or little green people. In addition to destroying the performance and reliability of the brain, with possible disastrous consequences in the form of serious accidents, catastrophic strategic errors, inappropriate familial or social behavior, etc., lack of sleep interferes with the activity of the immune system, therefore potentially making our organism vulnerable to all sorts of infectious diseases and probably also to many forms of cancer and immune system troubles. Another scourge of modern times, chronic nervous stress, also interferes with our immune system, both directly through the effect of endogenous corticoid substances, and indirectly by preventing us from sleeping adequately.

5.9 Dreams and hallucinations

The view of this article is that, unlike hallucinations, dreams occur to reorganize memory in order to improve its speed of access, and perhaps also to unwind successions of memories to characterize them as intermediate reinforcers, which in principle can also be made during wakefulness (sections 2.1.3, 2.1.5). Dreams are necessarily 'lived' because the formation of memories requires the neurons to reproduce actively the pattern to be memorized (section 2.1.2). GABA is the main neurotransmitter of the inhibitory neurons than prevent incoherent patterns from appearing simultaneously in neural arrays, as explained in sections 2.1.1 and 2.1.2, but there is a difference between dreams and hallucinations: during dreams, the entire region of the frontal cortex responsible for the highest level of coherence of our thoughts is subject to controlled deactivation, which allows the manifestation of incoherent internal lower-level neural activity, but through a mechanism that has no particular relation with GABA, except that this part of the cortex, like any other, uses GABA as well as other neurotransmitters; by contrast, during hallucinations caused by hallucinogens, this part of the cortex remains active but works incoherently because of the direct inhibition of GABA-mediated transmission by the drug. Therefore, the mechanisms of dreams and chemical hallucinations are different, but the results are similar, at least in appearance.

In principle, nothing prevents sufficiently powerful external entities from influencing dreams or hallucinations, although this is practically impossible to verify scientifically. As for the possibility of 'interpretation' of dreams, as attempted since the origin of human history until the times of Freud and beyond, in principle our proposal leaves some scientifically acceptable margin for dreams to represent unconsciously repressed wishes or impulses, through the

influence of these on the relative importance of the memories to be consolidated, which in principle can be assumed to determine the order in which these memories are processed. A similar phenomenon based on relative importance could, in principle, also be invoked for hallucinations.

Another important question about dreams and hallucinations is in what circumstances, if any, they can be remembered as real facts by otherwise normal people (that this may happen to mentally sick people is trivial). In principle, we will assume that dreams or hallucinations can be remembered as not real if the mind registers a memory of the mental process in which it realized that this dream or hallucination was not real, for example just after awakening. Therefore, if for some accidental reason this process is not registered, the dream or hallucination may be remembered as real facts. For example, let us consider the following (real) anecdote: someone is driving by night and suddenly sees a flying saucer landing on the road in front of his car. Fortunately, he wakes up immediately and realizes that he had fallen asleep for a few seconds. However, if he had suffered an accident with a blow on the head just after this vision, the memory of the fact that it was a dream might not have been recorded, and the result could have been that this person would have had the realistic impression of having collided with a flying saucer, which could have been rather embarrassing if it had been necessary to explain under oath the cause of the accident. More generally, in principle, any normal person could recall imaginary scenes as real in exceptional circumstances (accidents, intoxications, mental fatigue, etc.), or just doubt whether some past event was real or dreamed if it occurred a long time ago.

6. Conclusions

The main conclusions of our review of the aspects of artificial intelligence and related subjects in which people are usually interested are the following:

- It would be extremely unlikely that any machine built by humans could ever surpass or even just match the capabilities of the human mind to deal with problems of the real world. However, in principle machines could be superior for specific tasks related to artificial theoretical problems of human creation.
- Consciousness can be explained by purely physical phenomena with some changes in today's physical theories, but this is compatible with the existence of something corresponding to the traditional concept of soul and not accessible to scientific methods.
- It is extremely unlikely that any machine built by humans in the foreseeable future could be self-conscious or feel pleasure, suffering or other emotions, unless this machine is of biological nature.
- Consciousness can be considered a quantitative phenomenon, and therefore in principle most animals can be assumed to have some degree of consciousness, in proportion to their intelligence, and to be able to feel pleasure, suffering and other emotions. This also applies to any human creation of biological or hybrid nature and to any biological creature artificially created or modified by humans.
- Under any reasonable point of view, self-control and moral principles are an infinitely better strategy, for both the individual and the society, than hedonism, moral relativism, amorality or selfishness.
- Happiness cannot be reduced to a mere balance between pleasure and pain. It also involves criteria of dignity and moral principles, because most people can identify more or less happy periods in their lives, whereas the average balance between pleasure and pain cannot exceed a certain limit except over very short periods.
- There will almost certainly be life after death, because the basis of everything we are and know is the substrate and it is everywhere.

The following questions can be answered, at least for now, only on the basis of religious or metaphysical beliefs:

- Is there a duality soul + body or only a body?
- Will our moral behaviour in present life influence our fate after death? Of course, if we assume that God is perfect, then his justice must be infinite, so we can expect everybody to get what they deserve, before or after death.
- More generally, what form can we expect our life after death to take? In principle, it seems reasonable to assume that this form would not be too different from our current one, because otherwise we would probably no longer be 'ourselves'.

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